

Smoking Prevalence Among Indigenous Peoples of the World

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Introduction

To progress the United Nations (UN) *Sustainable Development Goals* and leave no-one behind in the process, it is necessary ‘to collect disaggregated data on population groups’ (UN, 2019, p.43.). The UN *Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People* (UNDRIP) recognises Indigenous peoples as distinct population groups with rights to self-determination. Necessary to that, Indigenous peoples ‘require information about their citizens, territories, and resources just like any other nation state’ (UN, 2008). Suppressing the collection or reporting of data on Indigenous peoples perpetuates invisibility that allows the neglect or abuse of their rights to continue without international objection.

A further challenge to achieving the goals of the UNDRIP is that, at the global level, other international treaties are not administered with thought for the UNDRIP. For instance, the World Health Organisation (WHO) recently recognised that Indigenous peoples are one of three groups being ‘left behind’ by the Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC) treaty parties (Glover et al., 2020). One way in which Indigenous peoples are being left behind, and it is likely a reason also, is the lack of monitoring of tobacco smoking and harmful tobacco-chewing amongst Indigenous peoples.

This report is a status report on tobacco smoking prevalence among Indigenous peoples of the world. But, people are more than any one behaviour in which they engage. Individuals have multiple roles and identities and can belong to multiple and intersecting social subgroups. They may be parents, leaders, teachers, guardians, healers, writers, artists. They are far more than just ‘a smoker’. Nobody should be defined by a single characteristic or behaviour, such as that they, in one moment or stage of their life, smoke or chew tobacco.

Tobacco smoking prevalence statistics are usually presented as an indicator of risk to personal health. Because of the immense, largely preventable, global disease burden and annual death toll attributed to tobacco use, tobacco has been demonised. Moralising about the evil of tobacco and stigmatising people who use tobacco has been deliberately deployed by public health to make tobacco use socially unacceptable. People who do not conform to non-smoking norms are deliberately impugned, discriminated against, and marginalised. This kind of social control is made easier when smoking tobacco is discussed without reference to the socio-historical, political and economic, environmental, and cultural context within which people start, and continue, to smoke. These contextual factors interact to determine whether someone will smoke, which subgroups will

smoke the most, and which tobacco products they will favour.

For this reason, we chose a COUNTRY FACT SHEET format. However, country borders are social constructs subject to change. The land or water realms Indigenous peoples historically belonged to or inhabited are not always replicated by the country borders of today. Imperialist expansion processes, such as war, colonisation, or alliances, have resulted in borders where previously none existed. Peoples and their lands or fishing areas have been divided and moved like stolen booty, or marbles won in a game of conkers. For example, African states and borders are distinctly artificial, and millions of Indigenous peoples have been displaced. Thus, we present countries grouped by the continent, ocean, or sea, within which they are located rather than contemporary UN recognised ‘regions’.

Who are we?

The Centre of Research Excellence: Indigenous Sovereignty & Smoking was established by Professor Marewa Glover, an Indigenous behavioural scientist with over 30 years experience in community and public health. Professor Glover’s work has mostly focused on reducing the harms associated with smoking tobacco, first in Australia and then in New Zealand (NZ). When she began working in public health in 1988, there were vast differences in smoking prevalence by ethnicity in Australia. Smoking rates were disproportionately high among the Indigenous people of Australia and NZ. For example, in 1992, smoking prevalence among NZ people aged 15 and over was 27%. But, this national average obscured what was happening for the Indigenous Māori population. At that time, around half of Māori adults smoked. Two statistics led to Dr Glover committing her career to reducing smoking among Indigenous people: 1) two-thirds of pregnant Māori women were recorded as smoking in 1992, and 2) lung cancer incidence rates in Māori men and women were the highest recorded in the world for men and women respectively (Public Health Commission, 1994).

A considerable amount of research has since been conducted in Canada, the United States of America (USA), NZ, and Australia showing a similar pattern of disproportionately high smoking rates among Indigenous people compared to the non-Indigenous populations that had become politically dominant in those countries. This led to our current research questions: were the higher smoking rates a unique experience just for these Indigenous peoples? Was the

colonisation process used on these peoples a determinant of smoking? Might loss of sovereignty, coupled with subsequent marginalisation, be a risk factor for smoking?

In 2006, Dr Glover presented at an international WHO consultation meeting with Indigenous people as part of the WHO *Indigenous Populations Forum on Tobacco Use*. At the time of writing, no report has resulted from that ‘Forum’ or the WHO on this topic.

The dream to progress the aspirations of Indigenous attendees at that meeting was the impetus for our application for funding from the Foundation for a Smoke-Free World. In 2018, we were successful in securing a grant from them to establish a research centre aimed at advancing knowledge on ways to more rapidly reduce tobacco smoking and tobacco chewing-related harm experienced by Indigenous peoples globally. This report is one output amongst a programme of research we are undertaking that includes: literature reviews, observational studies, and the design and testing of Indigenous solutions to reduce smoking-related harm.

Who are Indigenous people?

The UN estimates that 6% of the world’s population, about 476 million people living across 90 countries, are Indigenous people. Our investigation resulted in 105 countries being included in this report. Whilst many Indigenous groups are ‘officially’ recognised either in their country or at an international level, we found others who are still fighting for recognition of their status as a historically established, continuing, distinct tribal and cultural group.

For this project, we respected Indigenous peoples rights to self-determine their identity. An additional inclusion criterion was that the self-identified Indigenous people had been the predominant people resident and holding sovereignty in a geographical area prior to a different ethnic group moving in or taking over and gaining dominance over the governance of the area. In some places, the colonising group was a neighbouring group Indigenous to their area. The colonisation or annexation process and the result often involved Indigenous peoples being killed, displaced, or harmfully marginalised. This process is not just a historical peculiarity. It is an ongoing reality for some Indigenous peoples. We opted to include some peoples who currently may be seen to have regained political

dominance in their lands, but they remain economically dependent on colonising or colonised countries or their sovereignty status is vulnerable due to continuing demographic shifts and political instability.

The terms for referring to different peoples or groups varied in the sources we accessed. They were called ethnic groups, minority groups, first nations, or tribes, or they were identified by the region they lived in, such as the hill peoples. There was sometimes conflation of the names of tribes and their language. Multiple sources were read to clarify if a term was the name of a people versus a language or area name. In some places, it is an expedient and established practice to use a generic term that refers to all the tribes and sub-tribes sharing a close genealogical history and similar socio-historical-culture. For example, in NZ the term Māori came into use post-European settlement to more conveniently distinguish between the new arrivals and the ‘normal’ (Indigenous) people of the land. We have used these terms where it is common to do so, and especially when a term like Native Americans represents hundreds of tribal nations.

Methodology

Internet search engines, such as Google, were used to find the information contained in this report. The statistics are the latest we could find during a final pre-publication check of all links performed in January-February 2021. Scientific literature databases, like Google Scholar, were used to search for definitive reports on smoking among Indigenous peoples, but we were limited to English-language literature and we did not have time to conduct reviews for each country or region, apart from the one we have published on the Russian Federation (Merkin et al., 2021). One limitation is that the information contained online is constantly changing and link rot is a common problem. Comments on this report and suggested corrections are welcome.

The sources (links at the end of the report) provide a useful list of resources that may be of interest to students, Indigenous peoples, and their advocates.

The focus on the smoking of tobacco versus tobacco use of any sort

Tobacco and other plants containing nicotine have a long history of use among some Indigenous peoples of the world, dating back at least 8000 years. The

predominant tobacco product associated with the estimated 6.2 million largely preventable smoking-related deaths per annum globally is tobacco cigarettes (including loose ‘roll-your-own’ tobacco and cigarillos) mass-manufactured by giant multinational tobacco companies. For this reason, this report focuses on tobacco smoking prevalence, not other methods of tobacco use. Devices that heat tobacco (often called heat-not-burn devices) should have been excluded, but some countries incorrectly count the use of tobacco heating devices as smoking, thus inflating their smoking rates. The prevalence of vaping nicotine or use of oral tobacco or nicotine products is excluded. Information on the prevalence of use of these risk-reduced products by country is available elsewhere (see *Burning Issues: Global State of Tobacco Harm Reduction 2020*).

In the absence of more up-to-date scientifically established or officially collected data, the latest WHO tobacco use data for current smoking prevalence (includes daily and regular non-daily smoking) was used. If the WHO had no smoking prevalence data for a country, we used the *Tobacco Atlas*. However, the *Tobacco Atlas* provides daily smoking rates, which underestimates the prevalence of smoking in a country. Where daily, rather than current smoking prevalence appears, we have bolded the word ‘daily’ to emphasise the difference.

Where nations are located in the world is relevant to understanding smoking prevalence because the dispersal of the smoking of tobacco from the Americas to other islands and continents of the world has occurred at different rates. Reading this report you will see vast differences in smoking prevalence across different nations and regions.

There are varied differences in smoking rates by sex also. In the sources we used, smoking prevalence data were reported by sex for males and females only, excluding for example, non-binary. In some countries, hardly any females smoke. But, there are some peoples among whom females who smoke proportionately outnumber males who smoke. Where the data exists, we have provided the smoking prevalence for both males and females. Averaging across males and females can seriously misrepresent the risk of smoking and who is at greater risk, especially in groups with very high rates of smoking among males, but close to zero among females. Averages across sexes have also been used to direct the focus of interventions towards only males, causing neglect of tobacco chewing and smoking-related disease among females.

To gain a deeper understanding of stark differences in smoking by sex within a nation, further determinants of smoking could be useful. Future research should consider adding information about cultural and religious gender norms regarding the acceptability of smoking by gender.

Country information

We have included information about the size of countries, the size of the population, and the climate because population density and remoteness impacts behaviour dispersal also. Patterns of smoking tobacco might be affected by climatic conditions also, especially severe heat or cold, which may encourage smoking for warmth or suppression of hunger associated with weather-related food scarcity, for example.

The type of political system and economic status of a country are important determinants of smoking and the intensity and type of tobacco control interventions that may be implemented. Information on the extent to which a government is libertarian and respectful of human rights and dignity versus totalitarian is not provided but would be useful in a more comprehensive analysis.

Most of the countries in this report have signed up to the FCTC guidelines, and as a result, they are being urged to implement and enforce laws (regardless of the risk of harm) prohibiting the use of any and all tobacco products. Criminalising behaviours associated with tobacco product use represents a risk for Indigenous peoples who have disproportionately higher smoking rates than other ethnic groups, and who are disproportionately targeted by police, and incarcerated. Whilst a smoking-related ban in one country might not be enforced at all or may result in a manageable fine, in totalitarian countries the offender could be caned or imprisoned.

For each country, we have provided selected historical facts about when colonisation occurred and by whom. The colonising nation is bolded to distinguish substantial and sustained takeover from, for example, a temporary or limited occupation such as those that occurred during World War II (WWII).

We have also noted if each country supported the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People. Some countries have committed to the UNDRIP but have

done little more than that. For example, laws forbidding identification by ethnicity or forcing assimilation to the dominant culture have not been repealed. Practices that threaten the survival, dignity and well-being of the Indigenous peoples may be ongoing. At a minimum, countries that support the UNDRIP are being monitored.

Conclusions and recommendations

The mass-manufactured cigarette industry is an extractive industry, similar to other extractive industries that have been, and continue to, extract wealth from the land, sea, flora and fauna, crafts, knowledge, and bodies of Indigenous peoples. This extracted wealth is redirected to the shareholders and people who work in the tobacco and associated industries at all levels. A useful fact we could have included would be if a country's government was invested in the tobacco industry (available elsewhere see Just Managing Consulting, 2020). Many Governments use or capitalise on the tobacco industry (via taxes or settlement agreements) to extract income for their own needs. The China National Tobacco Company, 100% owned by the Chinese government, has the largest share of the tobacco cigarette market in the world (Just Managing Consulting, 2020). The most costly cigarettes are in Australia and NZ, netting the governments of those countries a proportionately massive income given their low national average smoking rates – a disproportionate amount of which is paid by the Indigenous peoples (e.g. NZIER, 2019).

Because of the health risk, but also the disproportionate extraction of wealth, the prevalence of the smoking of mass-manufactured tobacco cigarettes among Indigenous peoples is an important indicator of well-being and should be monitored.

The UNDRIP states that Indigenous peoples have the right to maintain their traditional ways of life and develop their culture. To be consistent with this right, policies and laws intended to stop tobacco use, including taxing tobacco products, must exclude tobacco growing, manufacture and use where those practices are part of the traditional way of life or a traditional source of livelihood or a craft of an Indigenous people. It is only the mass manufactured tobacco products of giant multi-national tobacco companies that should be the target of public health restrictions. In regards to Indigenous peoples who use these products, policies

aimed at reducing that use must be tailored to each country's context. For people or subgroups who do not have alternative capabilities or resources to meet the need that tobacco smoking or chewing was fulfilling, regressive measures can result in harmful unintended consequences.

The economic and social determinants of smoking are disproportionately higher among some Indigenous peoples. Some of them have also had traditional responses to such determinants suppressed or restricted by laws or policies intended to force their assimilation to the coloniser's culture. In some countries, Indigenous peoples are at disproportionate risk of negative discrimination and punishment by government authorities. Often in those same countries, structural racism results in inequitable access and delivery of healthcare, compounding the severity of smoking-related morbidity.

If countries have not first reduced inequity between the smoking rates of Indigenous people and non-Indigenous, when the tax on tobacco increases the price beyond what the lowest income groups can sustain without negatively affecting their spending on essentials (e.g. food) (Glover et al., 2019), it is these groups who pay a disproportionately high amount of the tax (NZIER, 2019). The result of the policies that the richest, politically and socially dominant groups support and can easily adapt to or workaroud, is that lowest income groups are kept immobile (Greene, 2019) at the bottom rung of the socioeconomic ladder. This immobility prevents them from escaping poverty and undermines their ability to participate in and influence society. As a result, they remain marginalised and unable to develop their distinctive economic, social and cultural way of life, as is their right. In this way, in some countries, tobacco control policies unintentionally may function as imperialist tools.

Disclosures

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Africa

Algeria

Location:

In Northern Africa, bordering the Mediterranean Sea to the north, Morocco to the west, Mauritania to the southwest, Mali and Niger to the south and Libya and Tunisia to the east.

Area:

2,381,741 sq km.

Climate:

Ranging from humid on the Mediterranean through to extremely hot and arid conditions in the Sahara desert.

Population:

43,576,691 (July 2021 est).

Indigenous people:

The Amazigh, of which there are many subgroups.

About Algeria:

Algeria has been ruled by many empires and dynasties from ancient times. The **Spanish** ruled from 1496 until 1516, when Algeria became part of the Ottoman Empire (1529-1830). The **French** established a colony in 1830. Following eight years of war against French rule, Algeria gained independence in 1962. Algerian Arabic and Berber are the native languages of over 99% of Algerians. French, though it has no official status, is widely used in government, culture, media (newspapers) and education. Algeria adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples but since 1992, has an ongoing policy of Arabisation.

Political system today:

Semi-presidential republic.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 27.1%; Females 0.5%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2006.

Angola

Location:

In southern Africa on the South Atlantic Ocean between Namibia and the Democratic Republic of the Congo.

Area:

1,246,700 sq km.

Climate:

Semi-arid in the south, with a cool dry season in the north from May to October; hot and rainy from November to April.

Population:

33,642,646 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The San, Himba and other Khoe-san descendent groups such as the Kwisi, the Kwepe, the Kuvale and the Zemba peoples.

About Angola:

Between the late 14th and mid-19th century, the Kingdom of Kongo stretched across central Africa from present-day northern Angola into the current Congo republics. The Kingdom traded heavily with the Portuguese who, from the 1700s, established coastal colonies and trading posts. By the 1800s, the Portuguese settlements had spread to the interior. In 1914, **Portugal** eradicated the last of the Kongo Kingdom and Angola became an entirely Portuguese colony. Angola gained independence from Portugal in 1975. Angola adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Semi-presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ age-standardised current prevalence was: Males 14.2%; Females 1.6%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2007.

Benin

Location:

On the Bight of Benin in the Gulf of Guinea bordered by Togo, Burkina Faso, Niger and Nigeria.

Area:

112,622 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and humid in the south and semi-arid in the north.

Population:

13,301,694 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

There are reportedly more than 50 ethnic groups. The Baatonu (meaning ‘the people’) also known as the Bariba, though of Sudanese origin are referred to as the natives as their occupation dates back to 1350.

About Benin:

The kingdom of Danhomé, (part of Benin), was established in the seventeenth century. **France** colonised Danhomé in the late nineteenth century, incorporating it into Benin. By 1904, Benin had become part of French West Africa. Self-governance occurred in 1958 and full independence was gained in 1960. Benin adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 8.1%; Females 0.2%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Botswana

Location:

Inland southern Africa.

Area:

581,730 sq km.

Climate:

Hot and dry for much of the year with a rainy season in summer.

Population:

2,350,667 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The San (also known as the Bushmen) peoples, the Balala people and the Nama people.

About Botswana:

In the 19th century three nations colonised Botswana: the **Netherlands, Germany and Britain**. In 1885, tribal chiefs travelled to Britain and successfully petitioned the British Government to place 'Bechuanaland' under British protection (the Bechuanaland Protectorate). Botswana achieved self-government in 1965, becoming the independent Republic of Botswana in 1966. Botswana adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 26.3%; Females 2.8%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Burkina Faso

Location:

In inland western Africa bordered by several surrounding nations including Benin, Togo, Ghana, Mali, and Niger.

Area:

274,200 sq km.

Climate:

Primarily tropical with very distinct wet and dry seasons.

Population:

21,382,659 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The pastoralist Peul also called the Duroobe or Egga Hodaabe peoples, and the Tuareg peoples.

About Burkina Faso:

In the late 19th century several European states attempted to move into the region, but it was the **French** who established a protectorate in 1896. Burkina Faso gained independence from France in 1960. The country adopted the name Burkina Faso in 1984. Burkina Faso adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 19.6%; Females 0.4%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2006.

Burundi

Location:

In inland central Africa bordered by Rwanda in the north, the Democratic Republic of the Congo to the east, Tanzania to the west, and Lake Tanganyika to the south.

Area:

27,830 sq km.

Climate:

Being just south of the Equator, Burundi is generally tropical with temperatures varying from an average cool to warm depending on altitude.

Population:

12,241,065 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Twa peoples.

About Burundi:

Burundi existed as an independent kingdom from the 16th century until it became a **German** colony in 1903. It was handed over to **Belgium** after Germany was defeated in WWI. Burundi gained independence in 1962. A series of military dictators controlled Burundi until 1993. In the same year, the country held its first democratic election. Burundi abstained from voting for the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Presidential representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 14.3%; Females 1%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Cameroon

Location:

In central and west Africa on the Bight of Biafra between Equatorial Guinea and Nigeria.

Area:

475,442 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical semi-arid in the north; humid and rainy elsewhere.

Population:

28,524,175 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

Those self-identifying as Indigenous include hunter-gatherer tribes known as the Bagyeli or Bakola. The Mbororo are pastoralists and the Kirdi communities live in the Mandara Mountain range.

About Cameroon:

Much of present-day Cameroon was ruled by chiefdoms before **German** colonisation in 1884. After WWI, the territory was divided up between **France** and **Britain** under a League of Nations mandate. French Cameroon gained independence in 1960. The following year the southern portion of neighbouring British Cameroon voted to merge with the new country to form the Federal Republic of Cameroon. In 1972 a new constitution was enacted and the country became known as the United Republic of Cameroon. Cameroon adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 14.8%; Females 0.3%. One 2013 cross-sectional study of Indigenous adults 20 years+ reported current smoking among Fulbe males at 5.8%. Smoking among Fulbe women was unclear but very low. Among their Mbororo participants, male current smoking was 3.9%. Similarly, smoking among Mbororo women was unclear but low.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2006.

Central African Republic

Location:

In central Africa north of the Democratic Republic of the Congo.

Area:

622,984 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical with hot dry winters and mild to hot wet summers.

Population:

5,357,984 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Mbororo Fulani, the Aka and the Litho peoples.

About Central African Republic:

The country became a **French** protectorate in the late 1800s. Independence was gained in 1960. The Central African Republic adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Presidential representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** prevalence was: Males 11.6%; Females 1.4%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Chad

Location:

A landlocked country in central Africa bordering Libya to the north, Sudan to the east, the Central African Republic to the south and Niger to the west.

Area:

1,284,000 sq km.

Climate:

There are four climatic zones: broad arid plains in the centre, desert in the north, dry mountains in the northwest, and tropical lowlands in the south.

Population:

17,414,108 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Bibbé Woila, the Dya-dyaé, the Fukarabé, the Fulani and the Wodaabé peoples.

About Chad:

The **French** colonised Chad in 1900. In 1905 Chad was linked to the federation of French colonial possessions in Middle Africa known as French Equatorial Africa. Chad gained independence in 1960. Chad was absent during the vote on the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 12.3%; Females 0.5%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2006.

Cote d'Ivoire

Location:

In western Africa on the North Atlantic Ocean between Ghana and Liberia.

Area:

322,463 sq km.

Climate:

A humid equatorial climate in the south and a dry tropical climate in the north.

Population:

28,088,455 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Bono, the Baoule, the Akye, the Anye, the Asante and the Aowin peoples.

About Cote d'Ivoire:

French and **Portuguese** traders arrived on the Ivory Coast (Cote d'Ivoire) to hunt elephants for their ivory, and by 1830 the French had built a permanent trading post. In 1958, Cote d'Ivoire began its journey to independence by becoming an autonomous republic. In 1960 the country gained its independence. Côte d'Ivoire abstained from voting for the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 20%; Females 0.3%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2010.

Democratic Republic of the Congo

Location:

In central Africa northeast of Angola.

Area:

2,344,858 sq km.

Climate:

An equatorial climate which is mostly hot, wet and humid, but with a cold alpine climate in the mountain areas.

Population:

5,417,414 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Mbuti (Bambuti) peoples, the Baka (Bacwa) and Batwa (Twa) peoples.

About Democratic Republic of the Congo:

The country was colonised by the **Belgians** in 1885. It is estimated that during Leopold's reign between 13-20 million people were murdered. After 75 years the Congo gained its independence in 1960. With independence the country changed its name to the Democratic Republic of Congo. In 1965, the country was renamed, Zaire but a later president changed the name back in 1997. The Democratic Republic of Congo adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Presidential representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2017, adult current prevalence was: Males 9.0%; Females 1.9%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Djibouti

Location:

In eastern Africa on the Gulf of Aden and the Red Sea, between Eritrea and Somalia.

Area:

23,200 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical desert.

Population:

38,413 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Somali and Afar peoples.

About Djibouti:

Djibouti was colonised by **France** in 1862. The country gained independence in 1977. In 1999 Djibouti held its first multi-party presidential election. Djibouti adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 21.6%; Females 2.8%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Egypt

Location:

In northern Africa on the Mediterranean between Libya and the Gaza Strip, with the Red Sea to the east.

Area:

1,001,450 sq km.

Climate:

Varies from surprisingly cold to extremely hot and in winter the northern coast is cool, windy and humid.

Population:

106,437,241 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Amazigh and Nubian peoples.

About Egypt:

The **British** colonised Egypt in 1882. The country gained its independence in 1956. This occurred following the signing of the Anglo-Egyptian agreement after the Suez Crisis and on the withdrawal of the British from the country. Egypt adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 36.3%; Females 0.2%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Eritrea

Location:

In eastern Africa on the Red Sea, between Djibouti and Sudan.

Area:

117,600 sq km.

Climate:

Hot, ranging from semi-arid to a desert climate and with cooler temperatures at higher elevations.

Population:

6,147,398 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Afar, Kunama, Saho and Nara peoples.

About Eritrea:

Italy was the first to colonise Eritrea, beginning in 1882. Control of Eritrea was then placed in the hands of the **British** after the defeat of the Italian armed forces in 1941. Then Eritrea became a British protectorate until 1951. In 1958 Eritrea became an autonomous state within the larger Ethiopian federation. This led to a 30-year struggle for full independence, which ended in 1991. Eritrea did not adopt the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 9.2%; Females 0.1%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Not a signatory.

Ethiopia

Location:

In eastern Africa, west of Somalia.

Area:

1,104,300 sq km.

Climate:

Lying in the tropics, it is hot in the lowlands but temperate on its elevated plateau.

Population:

110,871,031 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Berta, Gumuz, Shinasha, Mao and Komo peoples.

About Ethiopia:

Ethiopia is the oldest independent country in Africa. The Ethiopian monarchy maintained its freedom from colonial rule except for a short-lived Italian occupation from 1936-1941. In 1974 a military junta dethroned Emperor Haile Selassie. Ethiopia experienced bloody coups, uprisings, as well as wide-scale drought and massive population displacement, both internally and from other countries. The socialist government was toppled in 1991 by a coalition of rebel forces. A constitution was adopted in 1994 and Ethiopia's first multiparty elections were held in 1995. Ethiopia was absent during the vote on the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Federal parliamentary republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 5.4%; Females 0.3%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2014.

Gabon

Location:

In central Africa, bordering the Atlantic Ocean at the equator between the Republic of the Congo and Equatorial Guinea.

Area:

267,667 sq km.

Climate:

Hot and humid all year round in the north and inland areas, with a short dry season mid-year and cooler temperatures further south.

Population:

2,284,912 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Baka, Akowa, Bekui, Bebinga, Bambongo and Baringa peoples.

About Gabon:

Portuguese traders arrived in Gabon in the 15th century and named it 'Gabao'. The Dutch, English, and French set up human trafficking ports along the Gabon coast in the 16th century. Between 1862-1887 **France** expanded its position, taking full control of the country. Gabon achieved independence in 1960. Gabon adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 14.7%; Females 2.2%.

No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2009.

Ghana

Location:

In western Africa, with Burkina Faso to the north/northwest, Togo to the east, the Atlantic Ocean to the south and Côte d'Ivoire to the west.

Area:

238,533 sq km.

Climate:

Warm and tropical, varying from dry in the east, hot and humid in the southwest and hot in the north.

Population:

32,372,889 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Ashanti, Fanti, Brono, Akyem, Akwapim, Kwahu, Denkyira, Wassa, Nzima and Sefwi peoples.

About Ghana:

The **British** colonised Ghana in 1885. After 56 years of colonisation Ghana gained its independence in 1957. Ghana adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 5.2%; Females 0.1%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Kenya

Location:

In eastern Africa on the Indian Ocean coast, between the Jubaland province of Somalia and Tanzania.

Area:

582,650 sq km.

Climate:

Varies by location, ranging from mostly cool every day to always warm, and hot and tropical on the coast.

Population:

54,685,051 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Ogiek, Sengwer, Yaaku Waata and Sanya. The pastoral peoples include the Endorois, Turkana, Maasai and Samburu peoples.

About Kenya:

Before colonisation by the **British**, the Kenyan coast was frequented by Arab traders and later Portuguese traders. British rule began in 1920. The Mau Mau uprising led by the Kikuyu peoples (1952-1960) challenged British rule, however by 1960 the Mau Mau resistance had been defeated. Kenya gained independence in 1963. Kenya abstained from voting for the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 16.3%; Females 0.4%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Libya

Location:

In northern Africa on the Mediterranean Sea, between Egypt, Tunisia and Algeria.

Area:

1,759,540 sq km.

Climate:

The hot, arid Sahara dominates but on the coast the climate is Mediterranean.

Population:

7,017,224 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Amazigh peoples.

About Libya:

Libya was colonised by **Italy** in 1911. Libya became independent in 1951. Libya adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Political system today:

In transition. The Government of National Accord is an interim government formed under the terms of the Libyan Political Agreement, a United Nations led initiative signed on 17 December 2015.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 24.8%; Females 0.4%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Mali

Location:

In interior western Africa, southwest of Algeria, and north of Guinea, Cote d'Ivoire and Burkina Faso.

Area:

1,240,192 sq km.

Climate:

Hot desert in the north with long, extremely hot summers and scarce rainfall – overall hot, sunny and dry.

Population:

20,137,527 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Tuareg peoples.

About Mali:

Before colonisation Mali was part of the Sudanic empire, which included Ghana, Mali and Songhai. In 1898 **France** colonised Mali. In 1960, the Mali Federation, which included Senegal, gained independence. Mali is one of the largest countries in Africa, nevertheless it has a proportionately small population. Mali adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Semi-presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 18.1%; Females 0.6%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Mauritania

Location:

In western Africa on the North Atlantic Ocean, between Senegal and Western Sahara.

Area:

1,030,700 sq km.

Climate:

Most of its northern expanse is Saharan with one rainy season in the south from July to October.

Population:

4,079,284 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Bafour and the Soninké peoples.

About Mauritania:

Mauritania was previously part of the Moroccan kingdom. Colonised by the **French** in 1902 it became part of French West Africa. Whilst Arabic is the official language of Mauritania, Fula, Soninke and Wolof are also spoken and recognised as national languages. The country gained its independence in 1960. Mauritania was absent for the vote on the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 41.1%; Females 2.9%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Morocco

Location:

Borders the North Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea. It shares a border with Algeria to the east and Western Sahara to the south. Spain is close by to the north across the Strait of Gibraltar.

Area:

446,550 sq km.

Climate:

Most of Morocco north of the Western Sahara, particularly along the coasts, experiences a typical Mediterranean climate, with mild wet winters and hot dry summers. The rainy season generally extends from October to April, when occasional torrential rains will produce devastating floods.

Population:

36,561,813 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Amazigh people.

About Morocco:

Over the centuries, Morocco has had to defend its borders many times. It was a significant crossing point for trade between European and African nations. The Ottomans and the Europeans failed to establish a permanent foothold. In 1904, to ensure their position in Egypt, the British gave France authority in Morocco. In 1912, due to growing unrest in the country, the sultan asked for help and Morocco became a **French** protectorate. This lasted for 44 years. In northern Morocco, a **Spanish** protectorate lasted from 1912 until independence in 1956. In 1977, Morocco changed to a constitutional monarchy. Morocco has not adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Parliamentary constitutional monarchy.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 22.6%; Females 0.8%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Not a Party.

Namibia

Location:

In southern Africa on the South Atlantic Ocean, between Angola and South Africa.

Area:

824,292 sq km.

Climate:

The subtropical desert climate is characterised by great differences in day and night-time temperatures, low rainfall and overall low humidity.

Population:

2,678,191 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The San (Bushmen), Nama, Ovahimba, Ovazemba, Ovatjimba and Ovatwa together represent about 8% of the population.

About Namibia:

The **Portuguese** were the first Europeans to arrive in Namibia in 1485. In 1793 the Dutch arrived but were unable to hold on to their colony. The same situation occurred with the British attempt to establish a colony. **Germany** colonised Namibia between 1884-1890. Local resistance to German occupation was unsuccessful. During WWI, **South Africa** occupied the German colony. Namibia eventually gained independence in 1990. Namibia adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 23.1%; Females 4.5%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Niger

Location:

A landlocked country bordered by Libya and Algeria in the north, Benin and Nigeria in the south, Burkina Faso in the southeast, Mali in the west and Chad in the east.

Area:

1,267,000 sq km.

Climate:

Largely hot and dry desert, but with a tropical climate near the edges of the Niger River Basin in the south.

Population:

23,605,787 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Tuareg, Fulani and Toubou peoples.

About Niger:

The Portuguese pushed into Niger in the late 15th century. Trading included human trafficking with Britain, France, Germany and Spain participating. In the mid-1890s the **French** took control of Niger. Niger gained independence in 1960. Niger adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Semi-presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 12.6%; Females 0%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Republic of the Congo

Location:

Located on the western coast of central Africa, bordering Gabon to the west, Cameroon to the northwest and the Central African Republic to the northeast. The Democratic Republic of the Congo is to the southeast and Angola is to the south.

Area:

342,000 sq km.

Climate:

Equatorial, meaning it is hot and humid all year round with no real dry season in the north but with a dry and cooler season in winter in the centre and south.

Population:

5,417,414 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Mbendjele, Mikaya, Luma, Gyeli, Twa and Babongo peoples.

About Republic of the Congo:

The **French** colonised the Congo during 1897-1910. As part of their rule they merged the Congo with neighbouring colonies, creating a federation of French Equatorial Africa. Central to French rule was the creation of the Congo-Ocean Railway (1921-1934). The Congo became a republic within the French Community in 1958 and gained independence in 1960. The Republic of the Congo was the first country in Africa to pass legislation protecting Indigenous peoples' rights. The Republic of the Congo adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 23.8%; Females 0.5%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2007.

Rwanda

Location:

In central Africa, east of the Democratic Republic of the Congo and north of Burundi.

Area:

26,338 sq km.

Climate:

Temperate tropical highland climate with lower temperatures than are typical for equatorial countries, due to its high elevation.

Population:

12,943,132 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Batwa peoples.

About Rwanda:

Germany colonised Rwanda between 1894-1918. Belgian forces invaded Rwanda during WWI as part of the war effort against Germany. After Germany's defeat and as part of the League of Nations' post-war mandate, the country was handed to **Belgium**, whereupon it became the administering authority. Rwanda gained its independence in 1962. Rwanda joined the Commonwealth in late 2009. Rwanda was absent for the vote on the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 12.9%; Females 0.8%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Senegal

Location:

In western Africa on the North Atlantic Ocean, between Guinea-Bissau and Mauritania.

Area:

196,722 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical, with two well-defined humid and dry seasons resulting from northeast winter winds and southwest summer winds.

Population:

16,082,442 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Malinké, Sossé, Bambara, Dyula, Yalunka, Jakhanke and Soninke peoples.

About Senegal:

The **Dutch** West India Company purchased the island of Gorée as a port for trade in 1627. 'Ownership' of the island changed between the Netherlands and the **Portuguese** numerous times. Senegal was ultimately colonised by the **French** in 1664. Between 1780-1784 the French declared Senegal a French colony. Senegal gained its independence in the 1960s, after separating from the Mali Federation. Senegal adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 12.5%; Females 0.3%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Somalia

Location:

In eastern Africa, bordering the Gulf of Aden and the Indian Ocean east of Ethiopia.

Area:

637,657 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical, hot and dry all year. Rain in desert areas is scarce, while the wettest areas are occupied by savannah.

Population:

12,094,640 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Somali peoples.

About Somali:

Before colonisation, the Somali operated as clan republics without any central or overarching rulers. With the increasing demand for coal, European powers carved the Somali territory into four different territories. The four territories included **British** Somaliland, **French** Somaliland (later Djibouti), **Italian** Somaliland, and Kenya. In 1960, the former Italian and British Somaliland united to form the Somali Republic (Somalia). Mogadishu became the nation's capital. As part of this reunification Somalia voiced their desire for the inclusion of the subsumed region, Ogaden, into Somalia. Somalia gained independence in 1960. Somalia was absent for the vote on the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Federal parliamentary representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 13.1%; Females 1.6%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Not a party.

South Africa

Location:

At the southern tip of the continent.

Area:

1,219,090 sq km.

Climate:

Conditions range from temperate through to Mediterranean-like to sub-tropical. It mostly has warm sunny days and cool nights.

Population:

56,978,635 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Khoe-San/Khoisan, comprising the San and the Khoekhoe peoples. The main San groups include the San Khomani, the Khwe and the Xun tribes.

About South Africa:

The **Dutch** colonised Southern Africa in 1652, however the takeover was not absolute. Within 50 years of arriving the Dutch had set up settlements and the local Indigenous peoples had been displaced. After the British seized the Cape of Good Hope in 1806, many settlers of Dutch descent – Afrikaners, also called Boers – trekked north to establish Transvaal and the Orange Free State. The discovery of diamonds in 1867 and gold in 1886 spurred mass immigration from Europe. The **British** colonised parts of South Africa between 1795-1803 and 1806-1961. The country gained its independence in 1961. Between 1990 and 1993 the apartheid system was dismantled. South Africa adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Political system today:

Parliamentary republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 28.2%; Females 5.7%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Sudan

Location:

In north eastern Africa on the Red Sea, between Egypt and Eritrea.

Area:

1,861,484 sq km.

Climate:

Ranging from arid in the north to tropical wet and dry in the far southwest.

Population:

46,751,152 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

Various Indigenous peoples, collectively called the Nuba.

About Sudan:

In the 1880s British missionaries travelled into Sudan to convert the local tribes to Christianity. After the Mahdist War in 1895 a **British** (Anglo)-**Egyptian** force went into Sudan. In 1896 a **Belgian** expedition claimed portions of Southern Sudan. The **French** also began to claim parts of Sudan. In 1953 Britain and Egypt worked with the Sudanese government to bring about self-governance. In 1955 the Sudanese parliament declared Sudan independent. In 1956 Britain and Egypt recognised Sudanese independence. Sudan adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

Presidential representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2016, 18-69 years current smoking prevalence was: Males 17.1%; Females 0.7%. No data by ethnic group was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Tanzania

Location:

In eastern Africa on the Indian Ocean, between Kenya and Mozambique.

Area:

947,300 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical, with hot and humid coastal areas and cool temperate highlands. There are two rainy seasons though the central plateau tends to be dry all year.

Population:

62,092,761 (July 2021 est.)

Indigenous people:

The Akie Barbaig, Hadzabe, Maasai', Ndorobo, Parakuyo and Taturu peoples.

About Tanzania:

The first wave of colonisation began in 1506 when the **Portuguese** took control of the east African coast concentrating on Zanzibar, an integral trading port. By 1890, Tanzania had become a **British** colony, except for a strip of land overseen by **Germany** from 1880-1919. However, during 1919-1961 Britain retained full ownership of Zanzibar. In 1961, Tanzania gained independence. In 1963, Zanzibar gained its independence. Tanzania adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 16.6%; Females 0.6%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2007.

Tunisia

Location:

In northern Africa bordering the Mediterranean Sea between Algeria and Libya.

Area:

163,610 sq km.

Climate:

Winters are mild with moderate rainfall while the summers are hot and dry.

Population:

11,811,335 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Amazigh peoples.

About Tunisia:

For centuries, the Ottoman Empire had a major influence in Tunisia. **French** colonisation lasted from the end of the 19th Century through to 1956, whereupon Tunisia gained independence. Tunisia adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Parliamentary representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 34.7%; Females 1%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2010.

Uganda

Location:

In east-central Africa west of Kenya and east of the Democratic Republic of the Congo.

Area:

241,038 sq km.

Climate:

Warm tropical climate, with temperatures highest between December and February.

Population:

44,712,143 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Batwa, Karamojong and Benet peoples.

About Uganda:

British rule lasted from 1894-1962. The administration of the country transpired offshore with only a few British officials operating in the country. The British government relied on the 'Bakungu' chiefs to manage the country. Uganda gained independence in 1962. Uganda did not adopt the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Low income.

Political system today:

A presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 11.6%; Females 1.2%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2007.

Zambia

Location:

In southern Africa east of Angola south of the Democratic Republic of the Congo.

Area:

752,618 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical or sub-tropical depending on altitude with a hot wet season from mid-November to March and a dry season from April to November.

Population:

19,077,816 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Lozi, the Bemba, the Ngoni, the Tonga, the Luvale and the Kaonde peoples.

About Zambia:

The **British** colonised Zambia in 1888. After 76 years the country gained independence in 1964. Zambia adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

A presidential representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 22%; Females 1%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2008.

Zimbabwe

Location:

In southern Africa between South Africa and Zambia.

Area:

390,757 sq km.

Climate:

Subtropical conditions, due to high average elevation.

Population:

14,829, 988 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The San people.

About Zimbabwe:

Portugese colonialists moved into the region in the 16th century. The British began their incursions into the area in the 1880s. Cecil Rhodes' British South Africa Company, with a **British** mandate, initiated colonisation and named the colony Rhodesia. One hundred years later in 1980, after 15 years of bloody civil war, Zimbabwe gained independence. Zimbabwe adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 21.9%; Females 0.4%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2014.

The Americas

North America

Greenland

Location:

An island between the Arctic and North Atlantic Oceans, northeast of Canada.

Area:

2,381,740 sq km.

Climate:

Arctic climate with average temperatures not exceeding 10°C in the warmest months.

Population:

57,799 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

Kalaallit (Greenlandic Inuit).

About Greenland:

Kalaallit Nunaat means ‘The Land of the People’. During the 16th and 17th centuries, Dutch and English whalers frequently worked the seas around Greenland. The Norse, Swedish and Norwegians all attempted colonisation at different times between the 10th and 18th centuries, but the arctic conditions were difficult and thus prohibitive. **Danish** colonisation began in the 18th century. Greenland became an integral part of the Danish Realm in 1953. During WWII the USA gave Greenland protection from German invasion. Greenland voted in favour of increased self-rule in 2008 and acquired greater responsibility for internal affairs when the Act on Greenland Self-Government was signed into law in 2009. Denmark continues to exercise some control over Greenland. Denmark adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples after initially voting against it.

Political system today:

A self-governing parliamentary democracy within the Danish Commonwealth of the Realm.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ age-standardised **daily** smoking prevalence was Male: 42.7%; Females 44.3%. This likely slightly underestimates the Kalaallit prevalence but they do make up 89.5% of the population.

FCTC:

Not a party, however Denmark, which heavily influences tobacco control policy in Greenland, ratified the FCTC in 2004.

Canada

Location:

North of the USA, with the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans to west and east and the Arctic Ocean to the north.

Area:

9,984,670 sq km.

Climate:

A continental climate with very cold winters, hot summers and sparse precipitation.

Population:

37,943,231 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Métis and the Inuk (Inuit) peoples. In addition, there are more than 630 First Nation communities in Canada, representing more than 50 Nations.

About Canada:

Norse were the first Europeans to attempt to establish a settlement, but it did not last long and was eventually disbanded. Traders from many countries followed, including traders from Basque, Breton, Spain, Portugal, Britian, France and Ireland. By the mid-1600s the English and the French began to take control of the country. The **French** claimed the territory, calling it 'Canada', in the early 1700s. The **British** pushed further into the territory, establishing settlements in Newfoundland, Nova Scotia and Hudson Bay. In 1774 Britain and France signed the Quebec Act, which established a treaty that allowed them to coexist. France ceded Canada to England in 1763 through the Treaty of Paris. In 1867, with the merging of the three British colonies, Canada became a self-governing nation, but offically remained subject to British rule. Canada joined the British Commonwealth as an independent state in 1931. Canada was one of the nations that did not initially sign the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, but has since adopted it.

Economic status:

High income.

Political system today:

Federal parliamentary democracy under a constitutional monarchy. A Commonwealth realm.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2019, total population 12 years+ average current prevalence was: Males 17.3%; Females 12.3%. Many studies since 1983 have reported smoking rates for distinct Indigenous subgroups. Recently the government has begun to report average current smoking prevalence for all groups. In 2017, 15 years+ was: Métis Males 29.5%, Métis Females 27.7%; Inuk Males 63.3%, Inuk Females 59.8%; First Nations Males 35.3%, First Nations Females 35.1%. In 2017, the total population 12 years+ current smoking prevalence was: Males 19.1%; Females 13.4%.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

United States of America

Location:

Forty-eight of the states are in central North America between Canada and Mexico. Alaska is at the far northwest of the continent, to the west of Canada. Hawai'i is an island in the Pacific Ocean, west of the American continent.

Area:

9,833,517 sq km.

Climate:

Mainly temperate with notable exceptions, as in Alaska's Arctic tundra climate and Hawai'i's Pacific tropical conditions.

Population:

334,998,398 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

There are 562 Native American tribes on the mainland of America. There are also the Inuit and Yupik peoples of Alaska, and Native Hawaiians.

About United States of America:

The **Portuguese, Spanish, French** and the **Dutch** were the first European nations to establish settlements in America. In 1607 the **British** began colonising North America. The country gained its independence from Britain and established the United States of America with the Declaration of Independence signed in 1776. Alaska was 'claimed' by the **Spanish** in 1774 but left in 1793. **Russia** started to colonise parts of Alaska in 1741 but started withdrawing in the late 1850s. A formal transfer of Alaska was made to the **United States** in 1867. The U.S. Secretary of State purchased Alaska from Russia for approximately \$7.2 million. The **British** colonised Hawai'i in 1778. With the outbreak of the Spanish-American War in 1898 the United States annexed Hawai'i. Hawai'i was made a territory two years later in 1900. The USA holds sovereignty over several 'territories' that are not incorporated States of America. The populated territories are: American Samoa, Guam, the Northern Mariana Islands, Puerto Rico and the US Virgin Islands. Whilst the USA was one of the nations that did not initially sign the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, it has now adopted it.

Economic status:

High income.

Political system today:

Constitutional federal republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2019, 18 years+ weighted current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 15.3%; Females 12.7%. For non-Hispanic American Indians/Alaska Natives the prevalence was 20.9%. The 2018 data found that non-Hispanic American Indians/Alaska Native female smoking prevalence at 24% was higher than males at 19%. Prevalence likely varies widely by sub-group however. For example, current smoking for male and female adults 18 years+ 2000-2009 has been reported to be 42.1% among Northern Plain American Indians, which was higher than Southwest American Indians males at 18.8%, and females at 14.8%. Native Hawaiian combined with other Pacific Islander current smoking prevalence in 2018 was 22.6%. In 2016, smoking prevalence for Native Hawaiians alone was 27%.

FCTC:

Not a signatory.

Mexico

Location:

At the southern end of North America between the USA to the north, the Pacific Ocean to the west and south, the Gulf of Mexico to the east, and the Caribbean Sea, Belize and Guatemala to the southeast.

Area:

1,964,375 sq km.

Climate:

Generally arid on the west coast and in the central-northern highlands. It is moderately rainy in mountain plateaus and ranges and very rainy in some tropical southern areas.

Population:

130,207,371 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Náhuat, Maya, Zapoteco, Mixteco, Otomí, Tzeltal, Tzotzil, Totonaca, Mazateco and Chol peoples.

About Mexico:

Mexico is a central country for many Amerindian civilizations – including the Olmec, Toltec, Teotihuacan, Zapotec, Maya and Aztec. Colonised by **Spain** in the early 16th century, the country was administered by the Viceroyalty of New Spain for three centuries. It gained independence after the Mexican War of Independence, which lasted from 1808-1821. Mexico declared itself a pluricultural nation in 1992. Mexico adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Federal presidential republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, total population 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 19.7%; Females 5.9%. A 2012-2017 cross-sectional survey that collected data over 5 years with 2596 Mexican Amerindians from 60 different indigenous groups, found the overall current smoking was: Males 20.1%; Females 1.7%. This suggests that smoking prevalence among Indigenous males may not differ from the total male rate, but Indigenous females may smoke at lower rates than non-Indigenous Mexican females.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Central America and the Caribbean

Belize

Location:

On the northeast coast of Central America, bordered by Mexico, Guatemala and the Caribbean Sea.

Area:

22,966 sq km.

Climate:

A subtropical climate with distinct wet and dry seasons.

Population:

405,633 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Maya (Mopan and Kekchi) peoples.

About Belize:

The **Spanish** ruled Belize between the 16th and 17th centuries. The largest concentration of Maya peoples are still residents in the southern regions of the Yucatan Peninsula in Mexico and Belize. Belize gained independence in 1981. Belize adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Political system today:

Parliamentary democracy and constitutional monarchy. A Commonwealth realm, recognising Queen Elizabeth II as the head of state.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15-49 years current smoking prevalence was: Males 16.4%; Females 2.1%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Costa Rica

Location:

In Central America between Nicaragua to the north and Panama to the south, with the Pacific Ocean to the west and the Caribbean Sea to the east.

Area:

51,100 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and sub-tropical, with a dry season from December to April, a rainy season from May to November, and cooler temperatures in the highlands.

Population:

5,151,140 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Boruca, Bribri, Cabécar, Guaymí, Huetar, Maleku, Matambú and Térraba peoples.

About Costa Rica:

Before the colonisation of Costa Rica, it is estimated that 400,000-500,000 people lived in the area. Columbus landed in Costa Rica in 1502, however due to the country's climate and extremely difficult terrain, as well as lack of gold deposits, it was largely left alone until 1560 when the **Spanish** colonised the country. The Spanish named the land Costa Rica, which meant 'rich coast'. Costa Rica gained independence in 1821. The Costa Rica government adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Political system today:

A presidential representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 13.1%; Females 4.5%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2008.

Dominican Republic

Location:

Comprises the eastern two-thirds of the island of Hispaniola, which lies between the Caribbean Sea and the Atlantic Ocean, with Haiti to the west.

Area:

48,670 sq km.

Climate:

Generally hot, with tropical temperatures between 25°C-28°C all year and abundant rainfall from May to November.

Population:

10,597,348 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Taíno peoples.

About Dominican Republic:

The Dominican Republic was colonised by the **Spanish** in 1496 and, 348 years later, it gained independence in 1844. The Dominican Republic adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 10.6%; Females 4.8%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Not a Party.

El Salvador

Location:

In Central America, with Honduras to the northeast, Guatemala to the northwest and the Pacific Ocean to the south.

Area:

21,041 sq km.

Climate:

Warm, with temperatures varying with altitude from hot in the coastal lowlands to semi-tropical on the central plateau.

Population:

6,528,135 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Lenca, Maya Chortí and Maya Pocomam, Cacaopera and Nahua Pipil peoples.

About El Salvador:

El Salvador became a colony in 1521 after the **Spanish** invaded. Three hundred years later, in 1821, El Salvador gained independence. El Salvador adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 15.3%; Females 1.7%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2014.

Guatemala

Location:

In Central America, with Mexico to the northwest, the Pacific Ocean to the southwest, Belize and the Caribbean Sea to the northeast and Honduras and El Salvador to the southeast.

Area:

108,889 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and hot in the lowlands and cooler in mountainous areas at higher altitudes.

Population:

17,422,821 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Garífuna and Xinca peoples and also the Maya peoples: the Achi', Akateco, Awakateco, Chalchiteco, Ch'orti', Chuj, Itza', Ixil, Jacalteco, Kaqchikel, K'iche', Mam, Mopan, Poqomam, Poqomchi', Q'anjob'al, Q'eqchi', Sakapulteco, Sipakapense, Tektiteko, Tz'utujil and Uspanteko.

About Guatemala:

Between 1519-1521 the **Spanish** colonised Guatemala. It gained its independence in 1821 and was then governed by **Mexico** as part of the First Mexican Empire until its collapse in 1823. Guatemala then became part of the Federal Republic of Central America. This lasted until 1841 when the country finally gained full independence. In the 2018 census 43.6% identified as Indigenous and just over 50% were Mestizo, a term for people of mixed Indigenous and European descent. Guatemala adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 13.4%; Females 2.5%. In one study of Indigenous people from Santiago Atilán conducted in 2012-2013 13% of males reported that they smoked. No females reported that they smoked. A 2014-2015 study reported that 1% of Indigenous females smoked compared to 2% of non-Indigenous women.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Haiti

Location:

The western third of the island of Hispaniola between the Caribbean Sea and the North Atlantic Ocean, west of the Dominican Republic.

Area:

27,750 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and hot all year with temperatures slightly higher inland and on the southern coasts and slightly cooler on the northern coasts.

Population:

11,198,240 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Taíno peoples.

About Haiti:

The Taíno called the island Quisqueya (or Kiskeya), meaning ‘mother of the earth’. Haiti was colonised by **Spain** in 1492. In the late 1600s, **France** took possession of the western part of the island of Hispaniola, dividing the island into what is now Haiti and the Dominican Republic. Haiti gained independence in 1804. Haiti adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Semi-presidential republic.

Economic status:

Low income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 12.5%; Females 2.4%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

A signatory but not ratified since 2003.

Honduras

Location:

In Central America, bordered by Guatemala to the west, El Salvador to the southwest, Nicaragua to the southeast and the Pacific Ocean to the south, and by the Gulf of Honduras and the Caribbean Sea to the north.

Area:

112,090 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical, with a dry season in winter and rainy in summer.

Population:

9,346,277 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Lenca, Pech, Tawahka, Xicaque, Maya Ch'ortí, Misquito and Garífuna peoples.

About Honduras:

Honduras was colonised by **Spain** in 1502. The country gained its independence in 1821 after 319 years of colonisation. Honduras adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 19.6%; Females 1.2%.
No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Jamaica

Location:

A Caribbean island country located in the Caribbean Sea.

Area:

10,991 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and hot all year round.

Population:

2,816,602 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Taíno peoples.

About Jamaica:

Jamaica was colonised by **Spain** in 1494. Columbus named the island Santiago. In 1655 the **English** took control of the country. Jamaica gained its independence in 1962 after 161 years of colonisation. Jamaica adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary democracy under a constitutional monarchy, which recognises Queen Elizabeth II as the head of state. A Commonwealth realm.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was Males 14.2%; Females 3.4%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Nicaragua

Location:

In Central America, bordering the Caribbean Sea and the North Pacific Ocean, between Costa Rica and Honduras.

Area:

130,370 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical in the lowlands and cooler in the highlands.

Population:

6,243,931 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Chorotega people, the Cacaopera or Matagalpa peoples, the Ocanxiu or Sutiaba (and Nahoa or N.huatl) peoples, the M.skitu, Sumu-Mayangna and Rama peoples.

About Nicaragua:

The Pacific coast of Nicaragua was claimed as a **Spanish** colony in the early 16th century. Nicaragua gained independence in 1821 and became an independent republic in 1838. **Britain** occupied the Caribbean Coast in the first half of the 19th century, but gradually ceded control in subsequent decades. As at 2000, the majority of the population (63.1%) were Mestizo, people of mixed Spanish and Indigenous descent. Nicaragua adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 12.6%; Females 5.4%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2008.

Panama

Location:

In Central America, bordering Costa Rica to the northwest, Colombia to the southeast, the Atlantic Ocean to the north and the Pacific Ocean to the south.

Area:

75,420 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical maritime climate with a hot rainy season from May to January and a short dry season from January to May.

Population:

3,928,646 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Ngäbe, Buglé, Guna, Emberá, Wounaan, Bri bri and Naso Tjërdi peoples.

About Panama:

In 1510 the **Spanish** began their colonisation of Panama. For more than 300 years the country remained under Spanish rule, until it seceded from Spain in 1821 and joined the Republic of Gran Colombia – a union with Colombia, Ecuador and Venezuela. Panama became a state within Colombia when that Republic dissolved in 1830. Several countries (Britain, France, USA) worked first with Colombia and later with Panama to progress the construction of the Panama Railroad and Canal, and development of sustainable management structures. Panama gained independence in 1903 by way of a revolutionary junta, with US support, and promptly granted the USA rights to build and administer the Panama Canal Zone. The Panama Canal opened in 1914. Panama remained a **United States** protectorate until 1939. Governance and operations of the entire Panama Canal Zone, including the Canal, was transferred to Panama in 1999. Panama adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 8.1%; Females 1.8%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Puerto Rico

Location:

One of the islands of the Greater Antilles in the eastern Caribbean Sea, located 125 km (78 mi.) east of the island Hispaniola.

Area:

9,104 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and hot all year, though relatively cool from December to March.

Population:

3,142,779 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Taíno peoples.

About Puerto Rico:

The island was claimed by the **Spanish** in 1493. In conjunction with the colonisation of Puerto Rico, Spain shipped thousands of enslaved African peoples to the island in 1513. In 1898, following the Spanish-American War, the **United States of America** took control of Puerto Rico and it remains a territory of the US. Puerto Ricans gained US citizenship in 1917. Puerto Rico adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

A republican form of government subject to the jurisdiction and sovereignty of the USA. The head of state is the President of the USA.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2014, 15 years+ age-standardised current prevalence was: Males 16.4%; Females 6.8%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Not a signatory of the FCTC.

Republic of Cuba

Location:

A Caribbean island set between the Caribbean Sea and the North Atlantic Ocean.

Area:

110,860 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical, though moderated by trade winds and with a dry season from November to April and a rainy season from May to October.

Population:

11,032,343 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Taíno peoples.

About Republic of Cuba:

The **Spanish** colonisers arrived in Cuba in 1492. Cuba gained its independence in 1868, after 376 years of colonisation. In 1898, the **United States** expelled the Spanish. In 1930, the first attempt to oust the Americans failed. Cuba gained independence from the USA in 1961. Cuba adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Communist state.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 28.7%; Females 10%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Signed but not ratified.

Saint Lucia

Location:

An island in the Caribbean between the Caribbean Sea and the North Atlantic Ocean, north of Trinidad and Tobago.

Area:

616 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and hot all year round, with a relatively cool dry season from January to mid-April.

Population:

166,637 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Bethechilokono peoples.

About Saint Lucia:

The **French** established a colony on St Lucia in 1635. **Britain** took control of the island between 1663-1667. The French ceded St Lucia to Britain in 1814. In 1967, St Lucia gained self-governance, however Britain remained in control of St Lucia's external affairs and defences. In 1979, St Lucia became fully independent. St Lucia adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary democracy under a constitutional monarchy; a Commonwealth realm.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 14.3%; Females 1.8%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

South America

Argentina

Location:

In Southern South America, sharing land borders with Chile across the Andes to the west, with Bolivia and Paraguay to the north, and having the South Atlantic Ocean to the east.

Area:

2,780,400 sq km.

Climate:

The four main climate types are: warm, moderate, arid and cold. All are determined by the expanse across latitude, range in altitude and relief features.

Population:

45,864,941 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The 35 recognised Indigenous groups are the: Mapuche, Toba or Qom, Guarani peoples, Diaguita, Quilla (Kolla, Omaguaca), Quechua, Wichí, Comechingón,

Huarpe, Aonikenk or Tehuelche, Mocoví, Het peoples (Querandi, Pampa), Aymara, Rankulche, Charrúa, Atacama, Mbya-Guarani, Pilagá, Tonocote, Lulé, Chané, Sanavirón, Ona or Selk'nam, Chorote, Chulupi, Vilela, Ocloya, Alacaluf, Haush, Puelche and Yaghan.

About Argentina:

The **Spanish** began colonising Argentina in 1580. It was about 236 years before the country regained its independence in 1816. Argentina adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Federal constitutional republic and representative democracy.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 24.6%; Females 13.8%.

FCTC:

Signed but not ratified.

Bolivia

Location:

A landlocked country in central South America southwest of Brazil, with Peru and Chile to the east and Paraguay and Argentina to the south.

Area:

1,098,581 sq km.

Climate:

Although in the tropics, the temperatures range from equatorial heat to arctic cold.

Population:

11,758,869 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The 36 recognised Indigenous peoples of Bolivia are the Araona, Aymara, Ayoreo, Borôro, Canichana, Cayubaba, Chácobo, Chiquitano, Ese Ejja, Guaraní, Guarayo, Guató, Ignaciano, Itene, Itonama, Kolla, Leco, Machinere, Movima, Nivaclé, Pacahuara, Pauserna, Quechua, Maropa, Sirionó, Tacana, Tapieté, Toba,

Toromona, Trinitario peoples, Tsimané, Uru peoples, Wichí, Yaminawá, Yuqui and Yuracare people.

About Bolivia:

Bolivia began to be colonised by the **Spanish** in 1524. After 285 years of colonisation, it gained independence in 1809. In the 1970s, Bolivia experienced various coups, counter-coups and caretaker governments. In 2009 Bolivia officially changed the country's name to 'Plurinational State of Bolivia' to recognise its multi-ethnic nature and enhance the position of Bolivia's Indigenous peoples under the country's new constitution. Population projections for 2017 were that 48% of the population 15 years+ would be of Indigenous origin. Bolivia adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of the Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential representative democratic republic.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 22.3%; Females 11.8%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Brazil

Location:

In eastern South America, on the Atlantic Ocean. Brazil shares borders with nearly every other South American country.

Area:

8,515,767 sq km.

Climate:

Humid tropical and subtropical climate, except for a drier area in the northeast.

Population:

213,445,417 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

It is estimated that there are approximately 400 tribes spread across 26 states. The largest by population appears to be the Ticuna, followed by the Makuxi and the Guarani-Kaiowa/Pai Tavytera tribes.

About Brazil:

The **Portuguese** colonised Brazil in 1500. Portugal viewed Brazil more as an important trading post than a place to send larger numbers of settlers. During the Napoleonic Wars (1820), the Portuguese king fled to Brazil. The French made an unsuccessful attempt to establish a permanent colony in 1555. The Spanish made repeated efforts to gain territory in Brazil. In 1815, Brazil was elevated to a kingdom in union with Portugal. In 1822 Brazil gained independence. Brazil is the 5th largest country in the world, and the largest country in the Southern Hemisphere, being 10% larger than Australia. Brazil adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Federal presidential republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 15.3%; Females 8.2%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Chile

Location:

In southern South America lying alongside the Pacific Ocean, with Argentina to the east, Bolivia to the northeast and Peru to the north.

Area:

756,102 sq km.

Climate:

As Chile covers some 38 degrees of latitude, it experiences all climates except for the humid tropics.

Population:

18,307,925 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Mapuche, Aymara, Diaguita, Lickanantay, Atacama, Kolla, Quechua, Yahan, Yámana and Kawashkar peoples. There are also the Rapa Nui people of Easter Island, which is a territory of Chile.

About Chile:

The Inca rule stretched from southwest Ecuador to northern Chile and lasted a century until colonisation by the **Spanish** in 1530. Chile declared independence in 1810, but it did not gain full independence until 1818. In the War of the Pacific (1879-1883), Chile defeated Peru and Bolivia to win back its northern regions. Chile annexed Easter Island in 1888. Chile adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Federal presidential republic.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 38.8%; Females 30.1%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Colombia

Location:

In northern South America, with Panama to the northwest, the Caribbean Sea to the north, Venezuela to the east, Brazil to the southeast, Ecuador and Peru to the south, and the Pacific Ocean to the west.

Area:

1,138,910 sq km.

Climate:

Due to its proximity to the Equator, the climate is generally tropical (rainforest, savanna, steppe, desert and mountain). Each region generally experiences very little real change of seasons. Temperatures in each region vary little throughout the year.

Population:

50,355,650 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

There are 102 Indigenous peoples. These can be grouped as belonging to the

highlands or lowlands peoples, and then by their shared cultures. In the highlands there are Andean and Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta groups. In the lowlands there are many groups who are collectively referred to as belonging to a specific region, which are the Chocó, Amazonia, Guajira, Caribbean Coast and Urabá. There are also some other non-mountain peoples.

About Colombia:

The colonisation of Colombia began in 1525 with the arrival of the **Spanish**. The conquest of Colombia was completed in stages. The first stage began in 1499 and lasted until 1550. From 1525, colonisation saw Colombia become an integrated colony of the Spanish empire. Colombia gained independence 285 years later in 1810. Colombia became a republic and its independence was recognised in 1819. Colombia adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 10.8%; Females 3.3%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2008.

Ecuador

Location:

In western South America, bordered by Colombia to the north, Peru to the east and south, and the Pacific Ocean on the west. The Galápagos Islands are part of Ecuador.

Area:

283,561 sq km.

Climate:

Equatorial, so most of the country except for the Sierra is hot and humid.

Population:

17,093,159 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

There are approximately 14 Indigenous groups – including the Tsáchila, Chachi, Epera, Awa, Quichua, Shuar, Achuar, Shiwiar, A'i Cofán, Siona, Secoya, Zápara, Andoa y and Waorani peoples.

About Ecuador:

Ecuador saw the first wave of **Spanish** colonisers arrive in 1534. The Spanish created a confederation of Gran Colombia including Ecuador, Panama, Colombia and Venezuela. Almost 300 years later in 1830 Ecuador secured its independence from Spain and left the confederation. Ecuador adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 6.7%; Females 1.8%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2006.

Guyana

Location:

In northern South America on the North Atlantic Ocean with Suriname to the east, Venezuela to the west and Brazil to the south.

Area:

214,969 sq km.

Climate:

Hot, with heavy rainfall and small seasonal differences of high humidity, and high cloud cover typical of an equatorial lowland.

Population:

787,971 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Arawak (Lokono), the Warau, the Carib (Karinya), the Akawaio, the Patamona, the Arecuna, the Macushi, the Wapishana and the Waiwai peoples.

About Guyana:

The **Dutch** entered Guyana in the 16th century. Via treaty, they took over sovereignty in 1648. About 100 years later an influx of British immigrants began. They eventually outnumbered the Dutch and subsequent wars in Europe (1781-1815) saw Guyana being seized back and forth between the British and Dutch, with France governing for a two-year period. An Anglo-Dutch Treaty in 1814 ceded Guyana to **Britain**. Over 150 years later, in 1966, Guyana gained independence. Indigenous peoples make up approximately 9.2% of the country's total population. Most live in the hinterland. Between the 1970s and 80s, the government attempted to include the Indigenous population into its statistics. Guyana adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 22.1%; Females 2.2%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Paraguay

Location:

A landlocked country in central South America, northeast of Argentina, southwest of Brazil and south of Bolivia.

Area:

406,752 sq km.

Climate:

Subtropical to temperate, with substantial rainfall in the east and semi-arid conditions in the far west.

Population:

7,272,639 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The 19 Indigenous peoples are: the Guaraní, Aché, Avá Guaraní, Mbyá, Pai Tavytera, Guaraní Ñandeva and Western Guaraní, the Maskoy, Toba Maskoy, Enlhet Norte, Enxet Sur, Sanapaná, Angaité and Guaná, the Matabo Mataguayo,

Nivaclé, Maká and Manjui, Zamuco, Ayoreo, Yvytoso and Tomárahó, and the Guaicurú and Qom peoples.

About Paraguay:

The first Spanish settlements were established 1536. The **Spanish** colonised Paraguay in 1537. After 274 years of colonisation the country gained independence in 1811. In 1862 Paraguay started a war with Brazil. A Brazilian occupation army remained in the country between 1870-1876. Paraguay adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 17.3%; Females 3.9%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2006.

Peru

Location:

In western South America on the South Pacific Ocean, bordering Chile to the south, Bolivia and Brazil inland, and Ecuador and Colombia to the north.

Area:

1,285,216 sq km.

Climate:

Varies from tropical in the east to desert in the west, and temperate to frigid in the Andes.

Population:

32,201,224 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Achuar, Aguanó, Aguaruna, Amahuaca, Asháninka, Aymara, Bora, Candoshi, Cashibo, Chanka, Chincha, Cholones, Cocama, Cocamilla, Ese Ejja, Harakmbut, Huambisa, Jibito, Jivaro, Shuar, Kaxinawá, Kulina, Korubo, Machiguenga, Machinere, Maina, Mashco-Piro, Matsés (Mayoruna), Muinane,

Ocaína, Q'ero, Quechua, Secoya, Shapra, Shipibo-Conibo, Ticuna, Tukano, Urarina, Uru, Huanca, Witoto (Huitoto), Yagua, Yaminawá, Yanasha', Yine, Yukunas and Zaparo peoples.

About Peru:

The Incan Empire expanded throughout the 13th century to become one of the largest empires in pre-European America. Ecuador, Bolivia and parts of Argentina and Chile were all part of the Incan Empire at some point. **Spanish** colonisation began during the 15th century, culminating in the colonisation of Peru in 1533. After 291 years of colonisation and several wars between 1811- 1824, Peru achieved independence in 1824. Peru adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 14.3%; Females 3.1%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Suriname

Location:

Between French Guiana to the east, Guyana to the west, Brazil to the south and the Atlantic Ocean to the north.

Area:

163,820 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical, with a minor rainy season December through January and a minor dry season from early February to late April.

Population:

614,749 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Kali'na, Lokono, Trio and Wayana peoples.

About Suriname:

Suriname was colonised by the **Netherlands** in 1667. Between 1799-1802 and 1804-1815, the country came under **British** rule, only to be returned to the Dutch in 1816. The country gained independence in 1975. Suriname voted for the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Lower to upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 27.3%; Females 7.5%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2008.

Uruguay

Location:

In southern South America on the Atlantic Ocean coast, between Argentina and Brazil.

Area:

176,215 sq km.

Climate:

Generally a pleasant, temperate climate.

Population:

3,398,239 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Charrua and Guarani peoples.

About Uruguay:

The **Portuguese** first explored the region between 1512-1513. In 1680 they established a settlement on the northern bank of the La Plata river. In 1726, the Spanish established a settlement on the northern bank in an attempt to curb Portuguese expansion. By the 1750s, the **Spanish** had gained full control of the country. Whilst the British attempted to gain a hold in Uruguay, their colony never expanded. Uruguay gained independence from Spain in 1811, but was then annexed by Brazil until 1825. A three-year federation with Argentina followed, after which Uruguay became an independent nation in 1828. An economically and culturally influential, though small, informal British colony was established in Uruguay during the 19th to mid-20th centuries. Uruguay adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 22.7%; Females 16.2%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Europe

Finland

Location:

In northern Europe between Russia to the east, and Sweden and the tip of Norway to the west. Finland forms the northeast coast of the Baltic Sea. Estonia lies to the south across the Gulf of Finland.

Area:

338,145 sq km.

Climate:

Long cold winters and short, mild and moderately rainy summers.

Population:

5,587,442 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Sámi.

About Finland:

Finland has a long history back to around 9000 BC. As with most older countries, the Finnish Proper territories have grown and receded. **Swedish** colonisation of Finland occurred in the 12th century and 13th century. During this time Russia and Sweden fought over Finland. Between 1713-1721 **Russia** occupied Finland. During WWI and after the Russian Revolutions, Finland became an independent country. As the Finnish Proper population grew and expanded their area of habitation, the Sámi moved further north. There are approximately 10,000 Sámi in Finland. A law establishing the Finnish Sámi Parliament was passed in 1973, but Finland did not recognize the Sámi as a people until 1995. Finland adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples. Finnish Sámi face ongoing challenges to their way of life and freedom to continue traditional deer herding and fishing practices in their Sápmi lands.

Political system today:

Parliamentary republic.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 18.8%; Females 15.8%. A recent review did not find any data on smoking among the Sámi.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Norway

Location:

In northern Europe, on the North, Norwegian and Barents Seas, bordering Sweden, Finland and Russia to the east.

Area:

323,802 sq km.

Climate:

Western Norway has a marine climate, with comparatively cool summers, mild winters and high annual precipitation. Eastern Norway, sheltered by mountains, has warm summers, cold winters and lower rainfall. The uppermost areas of Norway are arctic.

Population:

5,509,591 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Sámi.

About Norway:

Norway has a long history, probably most famously known for the wide-ranging marauding and expansionary behaviour of the Vikings (Norse). Whereas the Sámi are a circumpolar people, the North Germanic Norse were Indigenous to the less cold southern and coastal areas. The Kingdom of Norway (uniting Norsemen) was founded in the 10th century. In 1397, after the bubonic plague pandemic (1346-1353) killed 60% of the population, Norway formed a union with Denmark that lasted more than four centuries. **Sweden** invaded Norway several times throughout history. In 1814, after the Napoleonic Wars, Sweden invaded and won the Swedish-Norwegian War. Norway was allowed to keep its constitution in return for accepting the Swedish King. A 1905 referendum led to Norway being granted independence. During WWII, Norway was occupied for five years by Nazi Germany. As in Finland, the southern parts of the Sápmi (Sámi lands) have been progressively diminished as non-Sámi Norwegians and businesses move north. The Norway Sámi population is estimated to be between 37,890-60,000. Norway adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary constitutional monarchy. The head of state is a constitutional monarch who exercises powers with the consent of the government.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 14.8%; Females 14.4%. A recent non-systematic review did not find any data on smoking among the Sámi. A systematic review of the broader health-focused literature might include such information. For example, one 2013-2014 study of periodontal health among 2078 adults aged 18-75 years in Finnmark County, North Norway, found the daily smoking rate, averaged across males and females, was: Sámi 20.5%; non-Sámi 23%. Whilst there is little difference between the Sámi and non-Sámi, the results suggest regional disparities exist.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Russian Federation

Location:

Spanning Eastern Europe and Northern Asia extending from the Arctic Ocean to the Black Sea and 17 bordering nations: Georgia in the southwest, Kazakhstan, Mongolia and China to the south, and the North Pacific Ocean in the east.

Area:

17,098,242 sq km.

Climate:

A continental climate dominates across the expanse of European and Asian Russia, except for the arctic tundra areas and the extreme southwest conditions.

Population:

142,320,790 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

More than 180 different ethnic groups, of which more than 60 are Indigenous. Only 47 have so far been officially recognised. In the far north are the Ainus, Aleuts, Alyutors, Chukchis, Chuvans, Dolgans, Enets, Itelmens, Kereks, Koryaks, Nenets,

Nganasans, Sámi, Siberian Yupik (Naukan and Sirenik), Veps and Yukaghir. In the Ingermanland region are Ingrians and Izhorians. In the far east are the Dungans, Evenks, Evens, Han, Koreans, Sakhalin Koreans, Nanai, Negidals, Nivkh, Oroch, Orok, Taz, Udege, Ulchs and the Uyghurs. Siberian peoples include the Chulym, Kets, Khanty, Mansi, Selkups, Siberian Tatars, Teleuts, Chelkans, Kumandins, Mongols, Shors, Soyots, Telengits, Tofalars, Tubalar and Tozhu Tuvans. The peoples from the Dagestan area include the Aghuls, Avars, Azerbaijanis, Dargins, Kumyks, Laks, Lezgins, Nogais, Rutuls, Tabasarans, Talysh, Tats and Tsakhurs.

About Russian Federation:

Founded in the 12th century, the Principality of Muscovy emerged after 200 years of Mongol domination, (13-15th centuries), to conquer and absorb surrounding principalities. Early 17th century saw Russia expand its rule over Siberia. During the 19th century, more territorial acquisitions occurred in Europe and Asia. Dissolution of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics, (1988-1991), has resulted in some contraction of Russia's territory, culminating in the formation of the Russian Federation. So far, 15 former Soviet Republics have been recognised as independent. The Russian Federation abstained from adopting the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Semi-presidential federation.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised smoking prevalence was: Males 40.1%; Females 15.4%. Since 1990, several studies, over years or across different groups, have reported on smoking among different Indigenous groups. The data was often combined to calculate averages which hides sex differences. For the period 1990-2015, smoking rates ranged from 24%-55% for females, and 46%-75% for males. There is no clear indication of reduced smoking rates over this period. Smoking prevalence likely varies by region and is different in remote communities.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2008.

Sweden

Location:

In northern Europe between Finland and Norway, bordering the Baltic Sea, the Gulf of Bothnia, Kattegat and Skagerrak.

Area:

450,295 sq km.

Climate:

Seasonal temperature differences are extreme, but generally the climate is temperate. Above the Arctic Circle winter temperatures drop below -30°C , though summer temperatures everywhere regularly hit $+20^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Population:

10,261,767 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Sámi.

About Sweden:

The Sápmi lands extend across the northernmost parts of Scandinavia from the North Atlantic Ocean in the West to and incorporating, the Kola Peninsula in the East. The Kola Peninsula and vast northern parts of what is now Norway, Sweden and Finland are part of the Sápmi. Exploitation of the Sápmi region with its Sámi people, colonisation, and forced assimilation by European rulers to the south, began in the 14th century. The Sámi have never stopped protesting the attempts to eliminate everything that is unique about them. Despite the modern-era division of the Sápmi across four European countries, the Sámi maintain a unified identity. Still, government and commercial interests continue to eat away at their Sápmi region. The Sámi Parliament of Sweden was established in 1993. It is a member of the Sámi Parliamentary Conference and Council, along with Sámi Parliaments established in Norway and Finland. The Kola Sámi have an Assembly pending Russian government approval to establish a similar Sámi Parliament. The Sámi Parliament does not yet have official representation in the Swedish parliament, but they are consulted. Sweden adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary constitutional monarchy.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 10.6%; Females 14.2%. Female smoking prevalence is higher due to a greater proportion of males having transitioned to smokeless snus products.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Ukraine

Location:

In Eastern Europe, with Russia to the east, Belarus to the north, Poland, Slovakia and Hungary to the west and Romania, Moldova and the Black Sea to the south.

Area:

603,550 sq km.

Climate:

Temperate continental climate, with cold snowy winters and warm summers.

Population:

43,745,640 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Crimean Tatar, Crimean Karaites and the Krymchaks peoples.

About Ukraine:

During the 10th and 11th centuries, Ukraine was the largest and most powerful state in Europe and the centre of the first eastern Slavic state, Kyivan Rus. It fell in later centuries to the Mongol empire, the Grand Duchy of Lithuania, the Kingdom of Poland and the Crimean Khanate. The War for Ukraine (1654-1667) resulted in **Russian** rule. From the late 1700s for 100 years, Ukraine territories were controlled by either Russia or the Austrian Empire. The Ukrainian People's Republic was declared following civil war in 1917-1921. Soon after, the resulting state became a founding member of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR). In the 1930s, USSR implemented a policy of Russification which required citizens to give up their non-Russian language and culture. Ukraine became independent with the dissolution of the USSR in 1991. Ukraine abstained from voting for the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples but endorsed it in 2014.

Political system today:

Semi-presidential republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 38.9%; Females 9.7%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2006.

Middle East

Iraq

Location:

A mostly landlocked country in the Middle East, with a harbour on the Persian Sea. Stretching back to the west, Iraq shares borders with several nations: Turkey to the north, Iran to the east, Kuwait to the southeast, Saudi Arabia to the south, Jordan to the southwest and Syria to the west.

Area:

438,317 sq km.

Climate:

Hot and dry, with long summers and short cool winters.

Population:

39,650,145 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Assyrian people.

About Iraq:

After the surrender of the Ottoman Empire in 1918, **British** forces took control over three provinces: Baghdad, Basra and Mosul. Iraq was formed from these three provinces and declared a British mandate by the League of Nations in 1920. Despite being granted their independence in 1932, a treaty held Iraq to certain obligations to Britain. During WWII, Rashid Ali, a nationalist who wanted to end Britain's influence, gained power with German aid. In response, a British-led Allied military campaign (the Anglo-Iraqi War) was waged and Britain regained control of Iraq. Britain reinstated the monarchy. A coup in 1958 overthrew the monarchy and Iraq was proclaimed a republic. Territorial disputes over borders and neighbouring regions, internal clashes over government type, leadership and direction, and ready foreign (United Nations, British and USA) intervention has seen an ongoing series of coups, wars and foreign military occupations. Iraq adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Political system today:

Federal parliamentary representative democratic republic.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 27%; Females 1.4%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2008.

Jordan

Location:

A mostly landlocked country in the Middle East, with a short coast at the north of the Gulf of Aqaba. Jordan shares a border with Saudi Arabia to the south and southeast, Iraq to the east, Syria to the north, and Israel and the West Bank to the west.

Area:

89,342 sq km.

Climate:

Ranges from a warm Mediterranean climate, through cold semi-arid and cold desert temperatures, to warm semi-arid and warm desert.

Population:

10,909,567 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

Arabian tribes known as Bedouins.

About Jordan:

Following WWI and the dissolution of the Ottoman Empire, the League of Nations awarded **Britain** the mandate to govern much of the Middle East, including Jordan. Britain demarcated a semi-autonomous region of Transjordan from Palestine in the early 1920s. The area gained independence in 1946 and became known as The Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. Jordan adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Political system today:

Parliamentary constitutional monarchy. The king exercises his power through the Prime Minister, Members of Parliament and judges he appoints.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2019, 18-69 years current smoking prevalence was: Males 66.1%; Females 17.4%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Asia

Bangladesh

Location:

In Southern Asia bordering the Bay of Bengal to the south, Myanmar to the east, India to the west and Bhutan to the north.

Area:

148,460 sq km.

Climate:

A subtropical monsoon climate characterised by wide seasonal variations in rainfall, high temperatures and humidity.

Population:

164,098,818 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

One 2012 report lists 59 peoples identifying as Indigenous. Only about 11 are officially recognised by the government.

About Bangladesh:

The huge delta region formed at the meeting of the Ganges and the Brahmaputra River systems are now referred to as Bangladesh. In 1517, the Portuguese installed an outpost at Chittagong. In 1755, a Danish station was established at Serampore. Between 1700-1947, the **British** gained a stronghold in the region. Bangladesh gained independence in 1971 after a nine-month guerilla war against the Pakistan Army. Between 1975-1990, the nation experienced military rule. A caretaker government was introduced in 1990 and the current parliamentary system was adopted in 1991. The Economist Intelligence Unit rated Bangladesh a 'hybrid regime' in 2019. The country did not adopt the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary republic.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 34.8%; Females 0.6%. One study that collected self-reported data in 2009 and 2011-12 from the tribal population, on all forms of tobacco, found a rate of 35.8%.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Cambodia

Location:

In southeastern Asia bordered to the south by the Gulf of Thailand, with Thailand to the north and west, and Vietnam to the east.

Area:

181,035 sq km.

Climate:

Cambodia has two seasons and a tropical climate with warm temperatures.

Population:

17,304,363 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

There are 24 Indigenous peoples: the Brao, Chhong, Jarai, Kachak, Kavet, Kel, Koang, Kuoy, Kreung, Krol, Phnong, La Eun, Lun, Mil, Por, Radei, Ro Ang, Sa Ouch, Sam Rei, Souy, Spong, Stieng, Thmoun and Tompuon peoples.

About Cambodia:

The country came under **French** protection in 1863, and it became part of French Indochina in 1887. Following the Japanese occupation in WWII, Cambodia gained full independence from France in 1953. In April 1975, after a 7 year struggle, the communist Khmer Rouge forces captured Phnom Penh. In December 1978, the Vietnamese invaded, driving the Khmer Rouge into the countryside, leading to 10 years of Vietnamese occupation. The 1993 constitution, which is still in force, was promulgated as a result of the 1991 Paris Peace Agreements, followed by elections organised under the aegis of the UN Transitional Authority in Cambodia. Cambodia adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary constitutional monarchy. The King serves as the head of state.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 30.4%; Females 1.8%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

India

Location:

In Southern Asia bordering the Arabian Sea to the southwest, Pakistan to the northwest, the Bay of Bengal and Bangladesh to the east and Bhutan, Nepal and China to the north.

Area:

3,287,263 sq km.

Climate:

Ranges from tropical in the south to temperate and alpine in the Himalayan north. The climate is strongly influenced by the Himalayas and the Thar Desert.

Population:

1,339,330,514 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

There are over 700 Scheduled Tribes and many more that are not recognised as such. India considers all Indians as Indigenous.

About India:

The Indus Valley civilization during the 3rd and 2nd millennia B.C. extended into northwestern India. About 1500 B.C. Aryan tribes from the northwest merged with the earlier Dravidian inhabitants resulting in the classical Indian culture. Several dynasties ruled over the subsequent centuries. In the 10th and 11th centuries, Turks and Afghans invaded India and established the Delhi Sultanate. In the early 16th century, the Mughal Dynasty began a reign that would last three centuries. European explorers began establishing footholds in India during the 16th century. Trade with India was highly valued by Europeans. The Portuguese set up trading posts in 1498. The Dutch East India Company and French also established trading bases in India. The British became interested in India for its raw materials. After the Sepoy Mutiny of 1857, the East India Company was abolished in favour of direct rule of India by the **British** government. During Britain's rule, indentured labourer schemes transported over one million Indians to Britain's other colonies to work, including for example, to Fiji, South Africa, Sri Lanka and Malaysia. India gained independence from Britain in 1947. India adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Federal parliamentary republic.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 12.1%; Females 0.4%. Several studies conducted during 1998-2014 have surveyed use of tobacco for smoking or chewing among Indian Scheduled Tribes. Studies varied in the age of participants included from 10-80 years. They varied in the products asked about, and tended to average across male and female use-rates, despite distinctive differences. Overall, smoking tobacco was likely more common among males, use of oral tobacco was higher than smoking tobacco, and prevalence rates varied widely by group.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Indonesia

Location:

A southeastern Asia archipelago of more than 17,000 islands. The country, as a whole, lies in the Indian and Pacific Oceans south of Malaysia, Singapore, Brunei and the Philippines, and north from Australia across the Timor Sea. Indonesia includes parts of Sumatra, Java, Bali, East and West Nusa Tenggara, Sulawesi, Timor, most of Borneo, West Papua and the islands of the Banda Arc.

Area:

1,904,569 sq km.

Climate:

Almost entirely tropical.

Population:

275,122,131 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The government does not fully accept the concept of Indigenous peoples. They recognise about 1,128 ethnic groups. Indonesia has spread across a vast area of

different island nations, so the number and diversity of Indigenous peoples goes way beyond the main peoples who are commonly named. For example, there are over 300 tribes in Western Papua alone.

About Indonesia:

The **Dutch** began to colonise Indonesia in the early 17th century. During WWII Japan occupied some of Indonesia. Indonesia declared its independence shortly before Japan's surrender, but it took 4 years before the Netherlands agreed to transfer sovereignty. Sovereignty was transferred in 1949. A period of sometimes unruly parliamentary democracy, martial law and an attempted coup was experienced through to 1967. The government then pursued a policy focused on economic development welcoming Western investment. 'Free and fair' democratic government has been experienced since 1999. Indonesia adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 60.2%; Females 1.9%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Not a Party.

Japan

Location:

In Eastern Asia. A chain of islands lying to the east of North and South Korea on the main East Asian coast across the Sea of Japan. Russia is to the northwest. China is to the southwest. The North Pacific Ocean is on the other side of Japan.

Area:

377,915 sq km.

Climate:

Japan has four distinct seasons with a climate ranging from subarctic in the north to subtropical in the south. Conditions are different between the Pacific side and the Sea of Japan side. Eastern Japan has hot and humid summers and cold winters with very heavy snow on the Sea of Japan side and in mountainous areas.

Population:

124,687,293 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Ainu and the Ryūkyūans (Okinawans).

About Japan:

Historically the Ainu people were residents of parts of Hokkaido, (the Northern island of Japan), and the Kuril Islands – (there is a dispute between Japan, the Ainu peoples and Russia over this island). Japan has a long history of immigration of peoples from East Asia, internal warfare and military-led, dynastic government. For more than 2 centuries from 1603, Japan closed to foreign influence and enjoyed relative political stability and development of their distinct culture. Between 1603-1868, the Japanese traded with the Ainu peoples, but Japan eventually took over the island of Hokkaido to secure its borders against Russia. Japan opened its ports after signing the Treaty of Kanagawa with the USA in 1854, and began to intensively modernise and industrialise. During the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Japan became a regional power that was able to defeat the forces of both China and Russia. It occupied Korea, Formosa (Taiwan), and southern Sakhalin Island. In 1931-32 Japan occupied Manchuria, and in 1937 it launched a full-scale invasion of China. Japan has not been formally colonised by any Western powers but has occupied other countries. Japan adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary constitutional monarchy.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 31.9%; Females 10.2%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Laos

Location:

In South East Asia, landlocked between Thailand to the west, Cambodia to the south, Vietnam to the east and Myanmar and China to the north.

Area:

236,800 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical with a pronounced rainy season from May through October.

Population:

7,574,356 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Khmou, Hmong, Phouthay, Tai, Makong, Katang, Lue and the Akha peoples.

About Laos:

The area has been inhabited for over 50,000 years and ruled variously by many kingdoms. In the 14th century the ancient Lao kingdom of Lan Xang established Laos. **Siam** (Thailand) took over in the 16th century. **French** colonisation began in the late 1800s. In the late 18th century to the late 19th century, Laos was part of French Indochina. The Franco-Siamese Treaty of 1907 defined the current Lao border with Thailand. By 1945, Laos began to move towards gaining independence. Full independence was gained in 1949. In 1975, a 6-century long monarchy was replaced with a strict socialist regime closely aligned to Vietnam. Laos adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

One-party socialist republic.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 39.9%; Females 4.9%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2006.

Malaysia

Location:

In south-eastern Asia on the Malay peninsula, bordering Thailand to the north with Indonesia to the south. Singapore is to the south across the Johor Strait. Encompasses the northern third of the island of Borneo south of Vietnam, bordered by Indonesia, Brunei, and the South China Sea.

Area:

148,460 sq km.

Climate:

Equatorial – hot and humid.

Population:

33,519,406 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

On Peninsular Malaysia there are 18 subgroups of the collectively called Orang Asli peoples. In Sarawak, the Orang Ulu or Dayak peoples include the Iban, Bidayuh, Kenyah, Kayan, Kedayan, Lunbawang, Punan, Bisayah, Kelabit,

Berawan, Kejaman, Ukit, Sekapan, Melanau and Penan. In Sabah, there are 39 different Indigenous groups known collectively as the Anak Negeri. The largest Anak Negeri groups are the Dusun, Murut, Paitan and Bajau.

About Maylasia:

Several powerful sultanates ruled on the Malay Peninsula and the island of Borneo in the 14th century. In the 16th century, the **Portuguese** established themselves in Malaysia, then surrendered to the **Dutch** in 1641. British interest came about due to the East India Company's need for a halfway base between India and China. Between 1826–1957, the **British** established colonies and protectorates in the area. During WWII, Japan occupied Malaysia. In 1948, the British-ruled territories on the Malay Peninsula (excepting Singapore), formed the Federation of Malaya which became independent in 1957. Malaysia was formed in 1963 when former British colonies of Singapore, as well as Sabah and Sarawak on the northern coast of Borneo, joined the Federation. Early independence was marred by communist insurgency, Indonesian confrontation, Philippine claims to Sabah, and Singapore's withdrawal in 1965. Malaysia adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Federal parliamentary representative democracy, with a constitutional monarchy. Most Malaysian Peninsular states have hereditary rulers commonly referred to as sultans. Melaka (Malacca) and Pulau Pinang (Penang), Sabah and Sarawak, have King appointed governors. Sabah and Sarawak retain certain constitutional prerogatives, such as maintaining their own immigration controls.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 36.3%; Females 0.8%. One 1994 study of Bajau adults 18 years+ found that the daily cigarette smoking rate was: Males 74.4%; Females 3.3%. Chewing tobacco was also strongly specific to gender, with only 4.3% of males chewing daily, but 77% of females chewed daily.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Myanmar

Location:

In Southeast Asia on the Andaman Sea and the Bay of Bengal, between India to the northwest, Bangladesh to the southwest, Thailand to the southeast, Laos to the east and with China to the north and northeast.

Area:

676,578 sq km.

Climate:

The climate is subtropical to tropical and has three seasons: a cool winter from November to February, a hot summer season in March and April and a rainy season from May to October, dominated by the southwest monsoon. Temperatures range from 21°C in the mountainous north to 32°C in the southern coastal and delta regions.

Population:

57,069,099 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

There is no accurate information about the number of Indigenous peoples in

Myanmar, primarily due to the government's claims that all citizens of Myanmar are Indigenous (taing-yin-tha). This position is contested by Indigenous rights groups. From the time of the 1935 census listing 135 ethnic groups, there appears to be repeated conflation of the terms ethnic and Indigenous.

About Myanmar:

Formerly known as Burma, Myanmar was an important trade route between China and India. The **Portuguese** arrived in Burma in the 16th century. Between 1824-1886, **Britain** fought a number of wars to gain control. The First Anglo-Burmese War began in 1824 and ended in 1826. The second began in 1852 and ended in 1853. The third war ran for less than a month during November 1885. Conquest complete, the British incorporated all the groups of Burma into their Indian Empire. Thus, Burma was administered as a province of India until 1937, when it became a separate self-governing colony. Following WWII, in 1948, Burma gained independence. Several groups maintain independent armies and control territory within the country, and they continue to seek autonomy. Myanmar adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People.

Political system today:

Parliamentary Republic. The military maintains a minimum 25% of parliamentary seats under the 2008 Army-drafted constitution. The armed forces control all organs of government. Nearly all ministerial and high-ranking political executives are also members of the military hierarchy. Following a military coup in February 2021, a state of emergency and martial law exists.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 29.8%; Females 2.3%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Nepal

Location:

A landlocked mountainous country in Southern Asia, bordered by India on the south, west and east. To the north lies what was once Tibet (a country subsumed by China in 1950).

Area:

147,181 sq km.

Climate:

Four distinct seasons are influenced by maritime and continental factors.

Population:

30,424,878 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

There are 59 recognised Indigenous peoples of Nepal. Collectively known as the Adivasi Janajati, they make up 35.8% of Nepal's total population. The 18 mountain peoples include the Bara Gaunle, Lhomi (Shingsawa), Thakali, Bhutia, Lhopa, Thudam, Byansi, Marphali, Thakali, Tingaunle Thakali, Chhairotan, Mugali,

Topkegola, Dolpo, Siyar, Sherpa, Larke, Tangbe and Wallung. The 24 hill peoples include the Bankaria, Hayu, Newar, Baramo, Hyolmo, Pahari, Bhujel/Gharti, Jirel, Rai, Chepang, Kushbadia, Sunuwar, Chhantyal, Kusunda, Surel, Dura, Lepcha, Tamang, Fri, Limbu, Thami, Gurung, Magar and Yakkha. The 7 peoples of the Inner Tarai are the Bote, Kumal, Raute, Danuwar, Majhi, Darai and Raji. The 10 peoples of the Tarai are the Dhanuk, Meche, Dhimal, Rajbanshi (Koch), Gangai, Satar, Jhangad, Tajpuria, Kisan Santhal and Tharu.

About Nepal:

For centuries, numerous dynasties ruled Nepal. During the late 18th to early 19th centuries, the Kingdom of Nepal was established. Nepal retained its independence following the Anglo-Nepalese War of 1814-1816, and the subsequent peace treaty laid the foundations for two centuries of amicable relations between Britain and Nepal. Nepal adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples

Political system today:

Federal parliamentary republic. The monarch has considerable political powers that can be used at their own independent discretion.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 29%; Females 7.3%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2006.

People's Republic of China

Location:

In Eastern Asia, bordering the East and South China Seas with Russia, Mongolia, and Kazakhstan to the north, Afghanistan, Pakistan and India to the west, and Nepal, Bhutan, Myanmar, Laos and Vietnam to the south.

Area:

9,596,960 sq km

Climate:

Temperate northern climate, with summer temperatures around 25°C and freezing winters. In the south it is subtropical, with very hot summers and mild winters.

Population:

1,397,897,720 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

China's government does not recognise the term Indigenous. Conflicting reports exist as to how many distinct ethnic groups there are in the area governed by

China. The Chinese government recognises over 56 groups, 55 of which are officially recognised as minority nationalities. External reports suggest there could be over 200 groups.

About People's Republic of China:

Many dynasties have governed China throughout history. The last was the Qing Dynasty. China was also colonised by **Britain**. China ceded Hong Kong to the British in 1841. **Germany** colonised China in 1860, leasing land in Northeast China. Today's China became a nation in 1912. Japanese forces took control of parts China in 1937. The independent People's Republic of China was declared in 1949. In recent times there have been several disputes over territory and borders. Additionally, forced cultural assimilation has been used to eradicate ethnic minority-group identification. Tibet, for example, was conquered by the Qing Dynasty in 1720. During 1913-1933, the Tibet Autonomous Region tried to regain their independence. In 1949 the Tibetans expelled the Chinese delegation in Lhasa but China responded by moving armed forces into the border town of Chamdo. A year of negotiation reportedly resulted in Tibet's authorisation of China's Central People's Government rule of Tibet. In 1956, a further uprising by Tibetan militia led to the Dalai Lama and others fleeing Tibet. China dissolved the remaining Tibetan Government. Exiled Tibetans continue to contest China's rule over Tibet. The Chinese Government adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

A semi-presidential socialist republic run by a single party – the Communist Party of China.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 43.7%; Females 1.6%. No data for Indigenous peoples was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Philippines

Location:

In Southeast Asia in the western Pacific Ocean, to the east of Vietnam across the South China Sea and bordered by the Philippine Sea to the east.

Area:

300,000 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and maritime, characterised by relatively high temperatures, high humidity and abundant rainfall. The coolest months fall in January with a mean temperature of 25.5°C, while the warmest month occurs in May with a mean temperature of 28.3°C.

Population:

110,818,325 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

With more than 100 ethno-linguistic groups, it is unclear how many Indigenous peoples there may be. Major groupings of Indigenous peoples include the Igorot,

Subanon, Tagbanwa, Aeta, Ati, Batak, Blaan, Bugkalot, Ibaloi, Lumad, Mangyan, Palawan, Suludnon, Tagbanwa, Tasaday, Tboli and Teduray peoples.

About Philippines:

The Philippines became a **Spanish** colony during the 16th century. The Philippines then became a territory of the **United States** in 1898 following the Spanish-American War. In 1946, the Philippines gained independence. By 1935, the Philippines was a self-governing commonwealth. Manuel Quezon was elected president and was tasked with preparing the country for independence after a 10-year transition. In 1942 the islands fell under Japanese occupation during WWII, and USA forces and Filipinos fought together during 1944-45 to regain control. The USA granted independence to the Philippines in 1946. The Philippines adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 37.7%; Females 6.1%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Taiwan

Location:

An island off the southeast of mainland China, separated by the Taiwan Strait. The Philippines lie to the south. Japan to the north.

Area:

35,980 sq km.

Climate:

Hot and humid from June through September, with typhoons common in July, August and September.

Population:

23,572,052 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Indigenous people who live on the plains are the: Arikun, Babuza, Basay, Hoanya, Kaxabu, Ketagalan, Kulon, Lloa, Luilang, Makatao, Papora, Pazeh, Qauqaut, Siraya, Taivoan, Taokas, Favorlang and Trobiawan. There are 16 officially recognised groups who live in interior mountainous regions: the Amis,

Ataal, Bunun, Kanakanavu, Kavalan, Paiwan, Puyuma, Rukai, Saaroa, Saisyat, Sakizaya, Seediq, Taroko, Thao, Tsou and Yami.

About Taiwan:

The Malayo-Polynesian peoples held on to their sovereignty for centuries until the early 17th century when the **Dutch** and **Spanish** began what has been called a form of co-colonisation. The Dutch encouraged migration from southern China to provide labourers. The **Ming Dynasty** fell in 1644, and loyalists fled to Taiwan and drove out the Dutch. In 1683, the **Chinese Qing Dynasty** took over parts of Taiwan. About 200 years later they declared it a province of the Qing Empire. In 1895, military defeat forced them to cede Taiwan to **Japan**, which then governed for 50 years. Following Japan's WWII loss, the Republic of **China**, with support from Britain, had the USA give Taiwan to them. In 1949, after the Chinese Communist Party won the civil war in China, 2 million members of the defeated Republic of China fled to Taiwan. They ruled under martial law until 1987, whilst claiming to be the legitimate government for mainland China and Taiwan. The country transitioned thereafter to democratic rule.

Political system today:

Semi-presidential democratic republic. The sovereign status of Taiwan is under dispute. The People's Republic of China claims Taiwan is a breakaway province which they intend to take back. The current government is seeking independence.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

One longitudinal 2001-2013 cohort study of people 12 years+ found current smoking rates were: Males 89.1%; Females 10.9%. One study of Taiwanese Aboriginals 20 years+ that collected data over 2005-2008 found a current smoking rate of 27.3%. A 2007-2009 study of Taiwanese Aboriginals 20-50 years found current smoking was: Males 74.1%; Females 38.9%. This was disproportionately higher than current smoking among the non-Indigenous counterparts in the study: Males 38.6%; Females 4.8%.

FCTC:

Not a member of the WHO and subjected to exclusion at China's request.

Thailand

Location:

In southeast Asia, bordering the Andaman Sea and Myanmar from north to south on the west, and the Gulf of Thailand, Cambodia and Laos from south to north on the east. Malaysia is to the south.

Area:

513,120 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical, with three distinct seasons – a hot season from March to mid-May, a rainy season from mid-May to October and a dry, relatively cooler season from November to February.

Population:

69,480,520 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Hmong, Karen, Lisu, Mien, Akha, Lahu, Lua, Thin and Khamu peoples.

About Thailand:

A unified Thai kingdom was established in the mid-14th century. Known as Siam until 1939, Thailand is the only Southeast Asian country never to have been colonised by a European power. A bloodless revolution in 1932 led to the establishment of a constitutional monarchy. A long history of coups and subsequent constitutions, 20 to date, coupled with, and partially due to a historical and cultural system of patronage, has resulted in widespread corruption of both private and government sectors. The last coup resulted in a change in the constitution that puts the entire political system under control of the army through the appointed Senate and through military-dominated oversight bodies. Throughout all of this, the monarchy has remained hugely popular. Thailand adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples in 2007 but does not officially recognise the existence of the Indigenous people.

Political system today:

Parliamentary (bi-cameral) democracy with a constitutional monarchy but the military are in control.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 36.5%; Females 1.6%. No data for Indigenous people was found.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Vietnam

Location:

A coastal country that extends from the Gulf of Tonkin in the north to the South China Sea. It shares a border with China in the north. Its inland western border is shared with Laos and further south by Cambodia.

Area:

331,210 sq km.

Climate:

A tropical monsoon climate with high humidity, but its varied terrain affects seasonal temperatures across different regions.

Population:

102,789,598 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

Very little is known of how many Indigenous peoples there may be in Vietnam. The collective name of Montagnard is typically applied to highland peoples of Vietnam, generally accepted as being the Indigenous people. The government

does not recognise the term Indigenous.

About Vietnam:

The conquest of Vietnam by **France** began in 1858 and was completed by 1884. The French subsumed Vietnam into their French Indochina in 1887. Vietnam declared independence after WWII, but France continued to rule until 1954. Under the Geneva Accords of 1954, Vietnam was divided into North and South Vietnam. Reunification occurred in 1976 when the North took over the South and renamed the whole the Socialist Republic of Vietnam. People of former South Vietnam were forced to undergo re-education. Vietnam adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Socialist republic with a one-party (communist) system maintaining a unitary government with centralised control over the state, military and media.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ current smoking prevalence was: Males 45.3%; Females 1.1%. No data found on Indigenous smoking rates.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Oceania

American Samoa

Location:

A group of islands in the south-central Pacific Ocean, north of Tonga, west of the Cook Islands, northeast of New Zealand and southwest of Hawai'i.

Area:

224 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and humid, with warm to hot temperatures all year and tropical storms more prevalent in the rainy season from November to May.

Population:

46,366 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

Samoaan people.

About American Samoa:

Settled as early as 1000 B.C., Samoa was not reached by European explorers until the 18th century. International rivalries in the latter half of the 19th century were settled by an 1899 treaty in which **Germany** and the **USA** divided Samoa. The USA formally occupied its portion, a smaller group of eastern islands the following year. In 1966, the UN gave American Samoa the option of joining the independent country of Samoa, but American Samoa chose to stay in the USA.

Political system today:

Unincorporated territory of the USA with local self-government following the USA State model of government, with an elected Governor, Lieutenant-Governor, and legislature.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2004, adults 24-64 years total population current **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 38.1%; Females 21.6%. In 2010, almost 90% of the population were Samoan. No later or ethnic specific data was found.

FCTC:

Not a Party, as a territory of the USA.

Australia

Location:

A large continent, and the second largest country after Brazil in the Southern Hemisphere. It is north of Antarctica and south of Asia, with the Indian Ocean to the west and the South Pacific Ocean to the east.

Area:

25,809,973 sq km.

Climate:

Temperate in the south and in southern coastal areas. Northern areas range from temperate to humid tropical. The interior ranges from temperate to hot, from dry desert, to tropical conditions in the northernmost areas.

Population:

25,466,459 (July 2020 est.).

Indigenous people:

There are more than 500 different Aboriginal clan groups across Australia and five Torres Strait Islander peoples.

About Australia:

The history of the Aboriginal people of the land dates back about 70,000 years. Europeans began arriving in Australia in the 17th century - the Spanish in 1601, then the Dutch in 1606. No formal attempts to take over the region, followed by colonisation, were made until 1770 when James Cook took possession of the east coast in the name of Britain. In 1829, **Britain** claimed the whole of Australia by misrepresenting Australia as terra nullius – meaning ‘land belonging to no-one’. That is, they denied that the existing inhabitants were people. The Germans arrived in 1838, settling in South Australia and Queensland. Six British colonies were formed by the late 18th and 19th centuries. They became federated and part of the Commonwealth of Australia in 1901. Australia became officially autonomous in both internal and external affairs in 1942, but did not sever the remaining British powers until the Australia Act of 1986. Australia was one of the nations that did not initially sign the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, but has since adopted it.

Political system today:

Federal parliamentary democracy under a constitutional monarchy; a Commonwealth realm.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2019, total population 14 years+ age-standardised current prevalence was: Males 15.9%; Females 12.2%. **Daily** smoking prevalence among Indigenous adults 18 years+ was: Males 46%, Females 41%.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Federated States of Micronesia

Location:

A widely dispersed archipelago in the northwestern Pacific Ocean, southeast of Guam and northeast of Papua New Guinea.

Area:

702 sq km.

Climate:

Equatorial – warm, humid and rainy throughout the year.

Population:

101,675 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Yapese, Ulithian, Woleaian, Chuukese, Pohnpeian, Kosraean, Nukuoro and Kapingamarangi peoples.

About Federated States of Micronesia:

Spanish colonisation occurred between 1525-1564. **Germany** purchased the islands from Spain in 1899. During WWI in 1914, Japan took control. In 1935, Japan established a military base on the island of Truk. By the end of WWII, the islands became part of the **USA** Territory for the Pacific (TTPI). The country gained independence in 1986. In 2010, the population were predominantly Indigenous. The Federated States of Micronesia adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Federal republic in free association with the USA.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ **daily** smoking current prevalence was: Males 20.8%; Females 6.5%.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Fiji

Location:

A South Pacific archipelago of more than 300 islands, lying to the east of Vanuatu and New Caledonia and west of Tonga, Niue and American Samoa. New Zealand lies directly to the south.

Area:

18,274 sq km.

Climate:

Warm tropical climate with maximum temperatures of 26°C-31°C all year.

Population:

939,535 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The iTaukei peoples.

About Fiji:

The Dutch explorer Abel Tasman landed in Fiji in 1643. Fiji was colonised by the **British** in 1874. From 1879, many Indian people were transported from India to Fiji by the British under an indentured labourer scheme. As many stayed on, this dramatically changed the demographics of Fiji. Today, almost half of the population are Indo-Fijian. After 96 years of colonisation, the country gained its independence in 1970. Between 1987-2006, Fiji experienced several coups fuelled by the inequities between the iTaukei and Indo-Fijians, and rise to political predominance of Indo-Fijian politicians. In 1990, the constitution enshrined political dominance to the iTaukei. Fiji was absent at the time of the vote on the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary republic.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 18 years+ current tobacco smoking prevalence was: Males 42%; Females 11%. In 2011, the **daily** smoking prevalence for iTaukei males and Indo-Fijian males was similar at 27% and 26% respectively, but the iTaukei females had a higher rate at 9.5% than Indo-Fijian females at 1%.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2003.

Guam

Location:

In the west of the North Pacific Ocean, roughly equidistant from Japan to the north, Papua New Guinea to the south and the Philippines in the west and Hawai'i far to the east.

Area:

544 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical hot and humid all year, with daytime temperatures around 30-32°C and 24-25°C at night.

Population:

168,801 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Chamorro people.

About Guam:

Guam was colonised by **Spain** in 1668. The USA captured Guam during the 1898 Spanish-American War which led to Spain ceding Guam to the **USA** in 1898. It was captured by the Japanese in 1941 and re-taken by the USA three years later. The military installations on the island are some of the most strategically important USA bases in the Pacific. They also constitute the island's most important source of income and economic stability. Guam remains a territory of the USA.

Political system today:

Republican form of government with separate executive, legislative, and judicial branches; unincorporated organized territory of the USA with local self-government.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, adult 18 years+ current smoking prevalence was: Males 28.3%; Females 15.2%. Among Chamorro adults, 31.3% were current smokers.

FCTC:

Not a Party, as a territory of the USA.

Kiribati

Location:

Consisting of 32 atolls and one raised coral island on the equator between the North and South Pacific Oceans, it lies south of Hawai'i, northeast of Fiji and American Samoa and northwest of French Polynesia.

Area:

811 sq km.

Climate:

A hot, humid, tropical climate, with temperatures closely related to the temperature of the surrounding seas.

Population:

113,001 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The i-Kiribati people.

About Kiribati:

Kiribati, once known as the Gilbert Islands, is one of the most isolated countries in the world. Kiribati became a **British** protectorate in 1892 and a colony in 1915. The island was invaded by the Japanese in 1941. Kiribati was granted self-rule in 1971 and complete independence in 1979 under its new name: Kiribati. The USA relinquished all claims to the Phoenix and Line Islands in 1979. Rising ocean waters are threatening to shrink Kiribati's land area. Kiribati was absent from the assembly at the time of the vote on the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Presidential republic.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 18-69 years age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 54.1%; Females 29.3%. Over 95% of the population are i-Kiribati.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Marshall Islands

Location:

A chain of volcanic islands and coral atolls in the central Pacific Ocean northeast of Papua New Guinea.

Area:

181 sq km.

Climate:

Equatorial – hot and humid all year.

Population:

78,831 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Marshallese people.

About Marshall Islands:

The **Spanish** claimed the islands in 1874, then the **Germans** claimed the islands from 1885-1914. The **Japanese** took over from 1919-1944 and then, following WWII, the **USA** took control from 1944-1986. The Marshall Islands spent almost four decades under USA administration. Between 1946-1958, the USA conducted approximately 67 nuclear tests at Enewetak Atoll. The fallout from the tests spread throughout the islands. The country gained its independence in 1986 via the Compact of Free Association. The Marshall Islands was absent from the assembly at the time of the vote on the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Mixed presidential-parliamentary system in free association with the USA.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2015, 15 years+ age-standardised current prevalence was: Males 22.8%; Females 4.2%. In 2006, over 90% of the population were estimated to be Marshallese and a further 6% were of mixed Marshallese and other descent.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Nauru

Location:

A central Pacific Ocean island, some 3000 km (1864 mi.) northeast of Australia and south of the Marshall Islands.

Area:

21 sq km.

Climate:

Stable temperatures all year, ranging between 24-25°C and around 30°C.

Population:

9,770 (2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Nauruan people.

About Nauru:

Once known as 'Pleasant Island', Nauru was colonised by **Germany** in 1888. Australian forces occupied Nauru in WWI. Nauru was captured by the Japanese during WWII. After WWII Nauru became a UN trust territory. The UN gave Britain, Australia and New Zealand a mandate over the island. Australia agreed to administer the mandate on behalf of the three signatories. Nauru gained independence in 1968. Nauru was absent from the assembly at the time of the vote on the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary republic.

Economic status:

Low to middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 18-69 years age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 37.9%; Females 37.4%. The majority of the population are Indigenous Nauruan.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

New Caledonia

Location:

A group of four inhabited and numerous uninhabited islands in the southwest Pacific Ocean. They lie south of Vanuatu, about 1210 km (750 mi.) east of Australia and west of Fiji.

Area:

18,575 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and warm or hot all year with temperatures seldom rising above 35°C.

Population:

293,608 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Melanesian Kanaks.

About New Caledonia:

James Cook landed on the main island in 1774 and named it New Caledonia. After being colonised by both **Britain** and **France** during the first half of the 19th century, the island became a French 'possession' in 1853. It was used as a penal colony for the French for four decades. Agitation for independence during the 1980s-1990s resulted in the 1998 Noumea Accord. Over two decades, an increasing amount of governing responsibility was transferred from France to New Caledonia. In 2018, a referendum was held to measure support for independence. Residents rejected any move towards it. A similar referendum was held in 2020 and independence was once again rejected. It has been suggested that another referendum be run in 2022.

Political system today:

New Caledonia is French sui generis collectively, with a government based on parliamentarism and representative democracy.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2010, adults 25-64 years current smoking (undefined) prevalence was: Males 48.7%; Females 39.1%. Indigenous people make up 39.1% of the population. No smoking data among the Kanak population was found.

FCTC:

Not a Party, as a territory of France.

New Zealand

Location:

Remotely sitting in the south of the South Pacific Ocean, New Zealand is the last major land mass before the Southern Ocean and Antarctica. Its closest neighbour is Australia's Norfolk Island, but the main continent of Australia to the west across the Tasman Sea is considered 'close', being about three hours away by plane. Many Pacific Islands are similarly a few hours by plane to the north.

Area:

268,838 sq km.

Climate:

Sub-tropical summer weather in the far north ranging through temperate conditions down to the South Island where it can reach -10°C in the alpine ranges during winter.

Population:

4,991,442 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The term Māori is used today as an overarching term for all the Polynesian tribes who

migrated south several centuries before European exploration of the Pacific.

About New Zealand:

The Dutch explorer Abel Tasman was the first European to reach New Zealand in 1642. He named the country New Zealand from the Dutch 'Nieuw Zeeland'. Dutch, French, Russian, German, Spanish, Portuguese and British, as well as North American sealers and whalers, used New Zealand as an outpost in the late 1700s and early 1800s. James Cook landed in New Zealand in 1769. From that time on a constant flow of migrants moved from the United Kingdom to settle in New Zealand. Their numbers grew to a disruptive proportion for the Indigenous Māori, leading them to petition the British Crown to better govern their settlers. The discussions culminated in the 1840 Treaty of Waitangi between over 500 Māori tribal chiefs and the **British** Crown. There were two versions with slightly different meanings. The English version is said to have ceded sovereignty to the Crown. The Māori language version said Māori tribes would retain sovereignty over their own affairs and lands. This has fuelled ongoing conflicts, protests and negotiations for reparation. Between 1843-1872, a series of wars were used to take land from many Māori tribes. The colony of New Zealand gained partial independence from Britain in 1907. Dominion status was attained in 1907, and full independence was granted in 1931 and ratified by New Zealand in 1947. Whilst New Zealand was one of the nations that did not initially sign the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, it has now adopted it.

Political system today:

Parliamentary democracy under a constitutional monarchy; a Commonwealth realm. Queen Elizabeth II serves as head of state over an independent government.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2019-2020, total 15 years+ current national smoking prevalence was: Males 14.2%; Females 12.6%. Māori Males was 27.4% and Māori Females was 35%.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Niue

Location:

A small island nation in the northwest of the South Pacific Ocean, Niue is encircled by American Samoa to the north, the Cook Islands to the southeast, Tonga to the southwest and Fiji in the west.

Area:

260 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical hot and wet from November to April with a drier period from May to October.

Population:

2,000 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Niuean people.

About Niue:

European contact began in 1774 when James Cook attempted to land on the island. In 1887, the King of Niue wrote to Queen Victoria requesting that Niue be placed under British protection. His request was turned down. Niue became a **British** colony in 1901. The country was handed over to New Zealand in 1901. In 1965, Niue was offered autonomy but asked for it to be deferred for a decade. Niue gained its autonomy to self-govern in 1974, but remains part of the realm of New Zealand. For example, Niue citizens continue to be New Zealand citizens.

Political system today:

Niue is self-governing, using a representative democratic dependency, in 'free association' with New Zealand. It is part of the Realm of New Zealand sharing the same head of state, Her Majesty the Queen in Right of New Zealand.

Economic status:

Relies heavily on aid from New Zealand.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ current smoking prevalence was: Males 22.6%; Females 13%. In 2011, about 80% of the population were Niuean.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Papua New Guinea

Location:

A group of islands, including the eastern half of the island of New Guinea, situated between the Coral Sea and the South Pacific Ocean, east of Indonesia, and north of Australia.

Area:

462,840 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical with temperatures between 23°C-28°C.

Population:

7,399,757 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

There are an estimated 600 distinct Melanesian Papuan tribes in Papua New Guinea and some Polynesian tribes in the South Pacific islands that are also part of Papua New Guinea.

About Papua New Guinea:

In 1889, New Guinea became a **German** colony, whilst Papua was declared **British**. In 1902, the latter area was transferred to **Australia** which occupied the northern portion during WWI. In 1946, the UN pressured Australia into handing over more administrative rights to the local government. Australia continued to administer the combined areas until independence in 1975. A nine-year secessionist revolt on the island of Bougainville ended in 1997. Since 2001, Bougainville, officially the Autonomous Region of Bougainville, has experienced autonomy. A 2019 referendum asking the population if they would like independence or greater self-rule occurred in November, with almost 98% of voters choosing independence. Conflicts emerged with the start of mining operations at Panguna. Australia declined any military support or backing of a political solution to the conflict. Bougainville independence is high on the government agenda for 2020 and beyond. Papua New Guinea was absent from the assembly at the time of the vote on the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary democracy under a constitutional monarchy; a Commonwealth realm. Queen Elizabeth II serves as head of state over an independent government.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2016-2018, 15-49 years current smoking prevalence was: Males 51.9%; Females 26.6%. The majority of the population are Melanesian Papuans.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2006.

Samoa

Location:

In the northwest of the South Pacific Ocean, neighbouring Tokelau to the north, American Samoa to the southeast and Fiji to the southwest.

Area:

2,831 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and humid, with distinct wet and dry seasons and little temperature variation.

Population:

204,898 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Samoan people.

About Samoa:

In 1889, **Britain** agreed to share control of Samoa with **Germany** and the **USA**. Samoa was then partitioned, with Germany taking much of the territory. Britain traded off their territory to gain concessions in Niue, the Solomon Islands, Tonga, and Africa. In 1914, the New Zealand government sent a military expedition to Western Samoa to take control and undertake administrative tasks for Britain. In 1927, the Samoan people staged a peaceful rebellion, however, New Zealand military police fired on the Mau demonstration, killing at least nine Samoans. In 1962 Samoa became the first Pacific Island state to regain its independence. In 1997, 'Western' was dropped from the nation's name, and it became known as Samoa. Samoa abstained from voting for the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary republic. The head of state is a constitutional monarch who only exercises powers with the consent of the government.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 18-64 years age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 32.3%; Females 13.9%. The majority of the population are Samoan.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Solomon Islands

Location:

A large group of over 900 islands in the South Pacific, to the east of Papua New Guinea and north of New Caledonia. There are six main islands, though more than 300 islands are populated.

Area:

28,896 sq km.

Climate:

Hot and humid all year with an average temperature of 27°C.

Population:

690,598 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Melanesian Solomon Islands peoples.

About Solomon Islands:

Spanish navigator Álvaro de Mendaña de Neira was the first European to visit the islands in 1568. He applied the name ‘The Islands of Solomon’. In response to the encroaching slave trade, the **British** established a protectorate over some islands in the Solomon Islands in the 1890s. The remainder under **German** jurisdiction were transferred to the British in 1900. Some of the most vicious fighting in the Pacific during WWII occurred on this archipelago. The Solomon Islands became self-governing in 1976 and independence was gained in 1978. The Solomon Islands was absent from the assembly at the time of the vote on the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary democracy under a constitutional monarchy; a Commonwealth realm. Queen Elizabeth II serves as head of state over an independent government.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15-49 years age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 46.6%; Females 16.2%. The population are predominantly Indigenous Melanesians.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Tahiti

Location:

Five archipelagos (Archipelago des Tuamotu, Iles Gambier, Iles Marquises, Iles Tubuai, Society Islands) in the South Pacific, west of South America, south of Hawai'i, and northeast of New Zealand.

Area:

4,167 sq km.

Climate:

November to April is the wet season and the average temperature ranges between 21°C-31°C with little variation.

Population:

297,154 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Tahitian people.

About Tahiti:

European contact with Tahiti was initially slow. The Portuguese arrived in 1521, the Dutch in 1722 and the British in 1777. The **French** colonised the country in 1834. In 1963, the French Government began testing nuclear weapons on the uninhabited island of Mururoa Atoll. After pressure from the Tahitian government and surrounding pacific nations, France moved testing underground in 1975. In 2009, the French government offered approximately \$10 million in compensation to those affected by the nuclear testing, but the government refused the offer. In recent years, French Polynesia's autonomy has been considerably expanded. France adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

A semi-autonomous territory of France, with its own assembly, president, budget and laws. France's influence is limited to subsidies, education, and security.

Economic status:

High income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2010, 18-64 years current tobacco smoking was: Males 38.5%; Females 43.6%. The 2020 estimate is that 78% of the population are Polynesian.

FCTC:

Not a Party, as a territory of France.

Timor-Leste

Location:

In Southeast Asia across the Timor Sea northwest of Australia, Timor-Leste is the eastern half of the island of Timor and includes the Oecussi region plus the islands of Pulau Atauro and Pulau Jaco.

Area:

14,874 sq km.

Climate:

Hot tropical climate with a dry and a wet season. Temperatures range between 25°C-35°C.

Population:

1,413,958 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Tetun peoples, the Mambae, the Tukudede, the Galoli, the Makasae, the Kemak, the Baikeno, the Bunak, the Fataluku, the Maubere, the Atoni people and there are reportedly many more.

About Timor-Leste:

Timor-Leste was colonised first by the **Portuguese** who arrived in 1520. From 1613 the **Dutch** began to replace them. The Portuguese took control of the eastern part of Timor island, whilst the Dutch controlled the western region. The conflict between the two countries led to a treaty in 1859, which saw the Portuguese cede the western portion of the island. Between 1942-1945 Japan occupied Portuguese Timor. The Portuguese resumed colonial authority at the end of WWII. East Timor declared itself independent in 1975, but was invaded and occupied by **Indonesia** nine days later. Indonesian occupation lasted until 1999. The East Timorese voted for independence from Indonesia in 1999. In 2002, Timor-Leste was internationally recognised as an independent state. Following a UN administered transition period, Timor-Leste adopted the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

A unitary semi-presidential representative democratic republic.

Economic status:

Low middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 15 years+ age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 62.8%; Females 4.8%. A majority of the population are Indigenous.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2004.

Tokelau

Location:

A group of three atolls in the South Pacific Ocean north of Samoa and further to the northeast of Fiji.

Area:

12 sq km.

Climate:

Hot, humid and rainy.

Population:

1,350 (2020 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Tokelauan people.

About Tokelau:

The first European visitors were a British commodore and his crew in 1765. French Catholic missionaries arrived between 1845-1870s. In 1863 Peruvian slavers kidnapped 253 men from one of the atolls. Between 1856 and 1979, the **USA** claimed that it held sovereignty over the islands. Tokelau became a **British** protectorate in 1877, and this was formalised in 1889. The British government annexed the country in 1916, along with the Gilbert and Ellice Islands Colony (Kiribati and Tuvalu). Through the 1900s American, Scottish, French, Portuguese and German explorers settled across the islands. The administration of Tokelau was transferred to New Zealand in 1925, making it a dependent territory of New Zealand. In 2006 and 2007 the population rejected changing to being in 'free association' with New Zealand.

Political system today:

Parliamentary representative democracy under a constitutional monarchy. Queen Elizabeth II in right of her Realm of New Zealand is head of state of Tokelau and is represented by an administrator appointed by the New Zealand Minister of Foreign Affairs and Trade.

Economic status:

High incomes but highly dependent upon financial aid from New Zealand.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2005, adults 25-64 years **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 54%; Females 49%. In 2016 over 70% of the total population were Tokelauan.

FCTC:

Not a party.

Tonga

Location:

An archipelago in the northwest of the South Pacific Ocean directly south of Samoa and southeast of Fiji.

Area:

747 sq km.

Climate:

Warm and tropical all year round and while hot in summer the temperature seldom rises above 35°C.

Population:

105,780 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Tongan people.

About Tonga:

The islands were visited by the Spanish and the French during the early 1700s. Captain Cook first visited Tonga in 1777. To avoid colonisation by Germany, Tonga became a **British** protectorate in 1900, meaning it was never officially colonised. In 1970 it withdrew from the protectorate and joined the Commonwealth. Tonga was absent from the assembly at the time of the vote on the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

A constitutional monarchy with a king who is head of state and commander-in-chief who appoints the Prime Minister from among members of Parliament.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 18-69 years age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 38.8%; Females 9.8%. Most of the population are Tongan.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Tuvalu

Location:

A group of nine islands in the South Pacific to the north of Fiji, northwest of Samoa and directly east of the Solomon Islands.

Area:

26 sq km.

Climate:

Warm all year with maximum temperatures between 31-32°C and minimums between 25-26°C.

Population:

11,448 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The Tuvaluan people.

About Tuvalu:

Tuvalu was first sighted by Europeans in 1568, by a Spanish commander. Colonised in 1892 by the **British** the country became known as the Ellice Islands. Later it became part of the Gilbert and Ellice Islands Colony in 1916. In 1974 the government held a referendum, which led to the country holding separate colonial status between 1975 and 1976. The country gained independence in 1978. With independence, the country changed its name to Tuvalu. Tuvalu was absent from the assembly at the time of the vote on the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary democracy under a constitutional monarchy; a Commonwealth realm. Queen Elizabeth II serves as head of state over an independent government.

Economic status:

Upper middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 18-69 years age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 43.5%; Females 17.6%. Most of the population are Tuvaluan.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Vanuatu

Location:

A group of 13 volcanic and coral islands in the southwestern Pacific Ocean to the north of New Caledonia and west of Fiji.

Area:

12,189 sq km.

Climate:

Tropical and subtropical with hot, humid summers from November to March when the temperature is 28-32°C. Tropical rains occur from December through February. A mild winter is experienced from April through to October with temperatures averaging 23°C.

Population:

303,009 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The ni-Vanuatu people.

About Vanuatu:

The Portuguese were the first Europeans to arrive in Vanuatu, in 1606, followed by the French in 1768 and the British in 1774. Colonised by both the **French** and the **British**, they jointly governed the country between 1906-1980. There was no cooperation between the two countries; they simply divided the country into two separate communities and each country governed their respective areas as they saw fit. Independence was agreed upon in 1977. In 1980, the country adopted the name Vanuatu, meaning 'Our Land Forever'. Vanuatu was absent from the assembly at the time of the vote on the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

Political system today:

Parliamentary republic.

Economic status:

Lower middle income.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2018, 25-64 years age-standardised current cigarette smoking prevalence was: Males 30.4%; Females 2.4%. Most of the population are ni-Vanuatu.

FCTC:

Ratified in 2005.

Wallis and Futuna

Location:

The Wallis and Futuna group of islands are situated in the west-central Pacific Ocean with Fiji to the southwest and Samoa to the east. The Territory includes three main islands, with a distance of 230 km separating Wallis from Futuna.

Area:

142 sq km.

Climate:

The Islands experience warm to hot South Sea tropical weather.

Population:

15,851 (July 2021 est.).

Indigenous people:

The 'Uvean, the Sigave and the Alo people.

About Wallis and Futuna:

Dutch explorers Willem Schouten and Jacob Le Maire landed on the island in 1616. They named it Futuna. In 1767 British explorer Samuel Wallis named the other island 'Wallis'. The French were the first Europeans to settle on the island in 1837. In 1887 a treaty was signed between France and the queen Uvea, (original name of the island known as Gutuna), making Futuna a **French** protectorate. The Wallis and Futuna people do not see themselves as ever having been colonised. It is said that the people decided to become part of the French Republic. In 1888 the kings of the islands Futuna and Alofi, (originally Sigave and Alo), also signed a treaty establishing a French protectorate. USA army forces occupied Wallis between 1942-1946. In 1959, the island nation voted to become a separate French territory. In 1961, this decree became official. In 2003, the island nation became a French 'overseas collectivity' which means the country has a high administrator and territorial assembly. Futuna has expressed a desire to have a separate territorial status from Wallis Island.

Political system today:

Wallis and Futuna is an overseas collectivity of France. It is divided into three districts that correspond to three traditional political paramount chieftaincies. A French-appointed chief administrator is the chief executive officer of the territory.

Economic status:

Heavily dependent on France.

Smoking prevalence:

As at 2009, adult 24-64 years **daily** smoking prevalence was: Males 61.9%; Females 27%. The majority of the population are Indigenous.

FCTC:

Not a Party, as a territory of France.

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